

Report on the SWOT analysis of entrepreneurial ecosystem

Deliverable D5

***ExcellEnt: Excellency in Entrepreneurship: Expanding European
entrepreneurship by boosting youth (self) employability and promoting a
sharing resources culture***

Horizon Europe Programme, Project number 101100515

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Current version:

v1.0, October 2023

Disclaimer:

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Deliverable Information

1. Grant Agreement #:	101100515
Project Title:	Excellency in Entrepreneurship: Expanding European entrepreneurship by boosting youth (self) employability and promoting a sharing resources culture
Project Acronym	ExcellEnt
Project Start Date:	January 15 th , 2023
Work Package:	WP2 – Connecting Entrepreneurial Ecosystems
Related Task(s):	T2.1 SWOT analysis of entrepreneurial ecosystems
Deliverable Title:	D5 Report on the SWOT analysis of entrepreneurial ecosystems
Deliverable Type:	R — Document, report
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Number of Pages:	121
Date of last Update	31 July 2023
Responsible Organization:	

History of changes

Version	Date	Prepared by	Comments
v0.1	July 31, 2023	iED	Document Structure and Guidelines
v1.0	October 14,2023	CREA	Deliverable document

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Abbreviations

BBAN	Bulgarian Business Angels Network
BDB	Bulgarian Development Bank
BPI	Banque Publique d'Investissement
BVCA	Bulgarian Private Equity and Venture Capital Association
CCI	Chambre de Commerce et d'Industrie (Chamber of Commerce)
CFE	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
EIF	European Investment Fund
EU	European Union
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDHC	Hellenic Digital Health Cluster
HEC	Hautes Études Commerciales (French Institution of Higher Business Education)
HEI	Higher Education Institute
ICT	Information and communication technology
INPI	Institut National de la Propriété Industrielle (National Industrial Property Institute)
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ISSS 2021-2027	Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization 2021-2027
MIR	Ministry of Innovation and Growth
NBU	New Bulgarian University
NSRF	National Strategic Reference Framework
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OPIC	Operational Program "Innovation and Competitiveness"
R&D	Research and Development
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
VC	Venture Capital
ZNNII	draft Law on the Promotion of Research and Innovation

Executive Summary

The concept of entrepreneurial ecosystems has been gaining considerable attention during the past decade among practitioners, policymakers, and researchers.

The **ExcelEnt project** in this report reveals the key findings of the entrepreneurial ecosystems in terms of ecosystem dynamics and contextualizing entrepreneurial ecosystems in the targeted economies. **The report provides detailed SWOT analysis of each country, to see the implications for the analyzed 6 countries (GR, TR, BG, UA, FR, IR) in fostering new venture creation.**

In order to collect information that can provide sufficient evidence for the process of developing interregional synergies on the **dynamics and characteristics of the entrepreneurial ecosystems**, specific data has been collected from the selected **6 countries** in the form of **National Country Reports**.

The main goal of this Deliverable is to support the targeted countries with actions, tools, workshops, travels to foster their entrepreneurial ecosystems through interregional collaboration and implement related strategic actions in interregional partnerships. It provides a step-by-step approach on how to identify and map the entrepreneurial ecosystems and existing linkages across countries, and how to design interregional Action Plans and implement related peer-learning exercises.

The **ExcelEnt** project aspires to explore novel ways to capture, preserve, curate, organise and communicate sets of unstructured entrepreneurial experiences, stories, narratives with an emphasis to those of younger audience that is addressing the challenge of (self)employability, so that they can constitute a shared resource that people can augment, and that individuals as well as institutions can delve into, to find inspiration for new ways of conceptualising and promoting entrepreneurship, and how these new ways can be reflected into every-day practices and policies, and foundations for visions of our common European future.

Introduction

A SWOT analysis can be a useful tool to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of an entrepreneurial ecosystem services framework. A SWOT analysis helps to identify the internal and external factors that affect the healthy growth of an entrepreneurial ecosystem framework and provide a basis for improving EE thinking, further embedding it in the key stakeholders decisions and management.

Two peers Deliverables provide insights on an EE framework to understanding of the six European ecosystems by examining three information sources: an in-depth country analysis, questionnaires and interviews as well as mapping of the ecosystem. This in-depth country analysis is the main goal of *T2.1 Report on the SWOT Analysis*.

This deliverable present the main

The D5 Stakeholder Collaboration Framework focuses on the process of the ecosystem mapping and assessment of the results from secondary resources obtained in the project, namely comparison parameters and questionnaires to entrepreneurs. The mapping itself is an ongoing task that will continue throughout the project and is expected to be sustained even beyond the completion of the project.

These deliverables within WP2 and WP5 , namely **D2.1 Report on the SWOT analysis of entrepreneurial ecosystem** and **D5.1 Stakeholder Collaboration Framework** are integral to each other and as such must be read collectively in order for the reader to gain a comprehensive overview of the ecosystems in Greece , Bulgaria, Turkiye, France, Ireland and Ukraine.

Scope of the SWOT analysis for the 6 entrepreneurial ecosystems

Based on an in-depth analysis of the information collected through WP1, a detailed SWOT analysis of the 6 ecosystems involved in the project is the main aim of D5 . Collecting the needs of entrepreneurial ecosystems, assessing their capacity and matching them with the best peers across the EU is one of the strategic objectives of our project. This task aims to engage in discussions with the local ecosystems and to address the challenges related to the maturity and inhomogeneity of resources

Purpose of the SWOT Analysis

The entrepreneurial ecosystem concept (EE) is becoming a cornerstone of contemporary sustainability thought . Challenges with this concept have not yet been systematically assessed alongside strengths and external factors that influence uptake. Such an assessment , SWOT, could form the basis for improving EE thinking, further embedding it into environmental decisions and management.

The EXCELLENT project partners from 6 countries have been completed a Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats (SWOT) analysis. Strengths include the approach being interdisciplinary, and a useful communication tool. Weaknesses include an incomplete scientific basis, frameworks being inconsistently applied, and accounting for nature's intrinsic value. Opportunities include alignment with existing policies and established methodologies, and increasing awareness. Threats include resistance to change, and difficulty with the local, national collaboration and the barriers in internationalization.

Consideration of SWOT themes suggest few strategic areas for developing and implementing EE.

The EE concept could improve decision-making, related to human resource use, and interpretation of the complexities of human-human interactions and interrelations among the key stakeholders.

It is considered that the EE framework could facilitate the understanding of the dynamics of the EE, ensuring decision-making that supports the sustainable development of the networks in the targeted countries and beyond.

Context of the SWOT Analysis

The context of the SWOT analysis on the European entrepreneurial ecosystem is the current situation and trends of the global and regional innovation landscape, such as the digital transformation, the green transition, the COVID-19 recovery, and the European integration.

The SWOT analysis also takes into account the existing initiatives and best practices that support the development of the ecosystem collected in 6 countries and formulated in National Reports.

Few initiatives are extremely important at the targeted countries such as La French Tech, Team Europe Initiatives, Erasmus+, EIT HEI Initiative, JRC STI for SDGs project, etc

The context of the SWOT analysis is important to understand the opportunities and challenges that the entrepreneurs (start-ups , woman-led businesses, self-entrepreneurs) face, as well as to provide recommendations and strategies to enhance their competitiveness, resilience, and impact.

The structure of the current Deliverable is follow :

Entrepreneurial Ecosystems Overview

- Introduction to each of the 6 entrepreneurial ecosystems under analysis.
- Key characteristics, geographical locations, and main stakeholders involved.

SWOT Analysis

Detailed SWOT analysis for each entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Strengths

- Identify and describe the internal strengths of the ecosystem that contribute to its development and growth.
- Discuss the advantages and assets the ecosystem possesses.

Weaknesses

- Analyse the internal weaknesses or limitations of the ecosystem that hinder its growth and development.
- Address the areas that require improvement or support.

Opportunities

- Explore external opportunities available to the ecosystem.
- Highlight potential areas for growth and collaboration.

Threats

- Identify external threats and challenges that could impact the ecosystem negatively.
- Discuss potential risks and ways to mitigate them.

Intended Audience

To create a comprehensive stakeholders' ecosystem we need to consider two key elements:

(i) who are the key stakeholders;

(ii) how to unite them coherently;

In the project, there are distinct stakeholder groups from six countries that will have various levels of power and influence. Here are the most important types of stakeholders to be included into the SWOT analysis.

Internal Stakeholders

Internal stakeholders are those people who are involved in the project. They are the project partners, managers. All these people are invested in the success of the project and, in a larger sense, of the company, in one way or another.

External Stakeholders

External stakeholders are not directly involved in **ExcelEnt** project, but the impact of the project will affect them. These can be everyone from suppliers to creditors and even public groups.

Internal Stakeholders

- Stakeholders of the ExcelEnt Project :

All **project participants** collaborating on the Project:

- **Institouto Anaptixis Epicheirrimatikotitas Astiki Etaireia (iED),**
- **International Development Ireland Limited (IDI),**
- **Creative Valley Groupe (CREA),**
- **Sabancı Universitesi (SAB),**
- **Sofia University ST Kiment Ohridski (UNISOFIA),**
- **TechUkraine (TU)**
- **BOOSTER LABS S.A.S (BOOST)**

External Stakeholders

The project partners have defined the main stakeholders in their own country . Extracts come from the 6 National Reports.

- Universities (Business Schools)
- Business incubators/accelerators
- Entrepreneurs
- Policy makers

Methodology

Approach and methods used to collect information and data for the SWOT analysis. Sources of information description, such as interviews and data analysis sources.

The Methodology included:

Desk Research: existing literature related to the entrepreneurial ecosystems. This may involve reports, academic publications, and relevant online resources to gain insights into the historical and current state of each ecosystem.

Data Analysis: statistical data related to the entrepreneurial ecosystems, such as economic indicators, employment rates, funding trends, and business growth. This quantitative analysis should aim in identifying patterns, trends, and areas of strength or concern within the ecosystems.

Survey: we may create an online survey and distribute it among stakeholders within our ecosystem. The aim of the survey will be to capture valuable perspectives on the ecosystem's performance, challenges, and potential areas of improvement. We need to discuss this in August's online meeting.

Interviews: Valuable insights and feedback gathered from the interviews conducted under Task 1.1.

It was an important aspect to prepare carefully the data collection and analysis process, to provide an initial entrepreneurial ecosystem overview to perform cross-country analysis, that included the following step:

- It was important to focus on the data collection, the relevant indicators and not overload the users with too many indicators; careful selection is key, especially for priority areas for thematic and horizontal corporations to have enough inputs for the SWOT analysis.
- Being creative and persistent with the data collection was necessary; some ecosystems do not have sufficient data readily available. To collect data on-site, either through interviews, or, where time and resources allow it, through targeted surveys with stakeholders, there was a need for competent data-researchers.
- Determining all the factors of the ecosystems, it relies not only on a quantitative data analysis process but requires a qualitative data interpretation and crosschecking/validation with the regional stakeholders.

Entrepreneurial Ecosystems Overview

- *Introduction to each of the 6 entrepreneurial ecosystems under analysis.*

Greece

The entrepreneurial ecosystem in Greece is an evolving landscape marked by increasing dynamism, collaboration, and innovation. Despite facing challenges related to regulatory complexities and economic constraints, the Greek startup environment has displayed remarkable resilience and adaptability. Fuelled by a highly educated talent pool, supportive government policies, and a culture that values both traditional sectors and technological innovation, the ecosystem offers a fertile ground for entrepreneurship. Initiatives like Elevate Greece [1] play a pivotal role in connecting key stakeholders, thereby facilitating partnerships and resources essential for startup growth. From healthcare and technology to energy and tourism, the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem exhibits a unique blend of traditional expertise and modern innovation, making it an attractive hub for both domestic and international entrepreneurs.

Bulgaria

The Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem has witnessed significant growth and transformation during recent years. For example, as of 2023, it is ranked 38th worldwide in the Global Startup Ecosystem Index [1]. Bulgaria is progressively positioning itself as a digital-forward nation, emphasizing the integration of advanced technologies into its entrepreneurial landscape. The country has been making strides in enhancing its digital infrastructure. Furthermore, the nation is actively working on the development of new generations of digital technologies, recognizing their potential to reshape the economy in the coming decades. However, despite these advancements, there's room for improvement, especially in terms of digital public services where Bulgaria lags behind the EU average.

Given this context, Bulgaria's entrepreneurial ecosystem can be described as one that is increasingly digital-centric, with a focus on integrating modern technologies into various sectors. The nation has recognized the importance of the ICT sector, with efforts being made to strengthen its ties with other domains like mechatronics and microelectronics. This is seen as a pivotal step towards broader digitalization in areas such as clean technology, telemedicine, and teleeducation. The government's commitment to this cause is further highlighted by its investment in human capital, promotion of

business investment in digital innovation, and emphasis on increasing the digital literacy of the workforce.

In light of the above, the Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem can be characterized by its robust digital infrastructure, diverse support programs, and a rich pool of tech talent. The country has laid a solid foundation for startups, with a conducive environment that includes accelerators, incubators, and a strong emphasis on ICT integration across sectors. However, to truly capitalize on its potential, Bulgaria must continue to prioritize digital transformation, foster innovation, and ensure that its strategies align with the evolving global tech landscape.

Turkiye

With geographical and cultural proximity to several countries, a large domestic market and dynamic economy, and enabling institutions growing both in quantity and quality, Turkiye offers unique advantages for the entrepreneurs to start and scale their businesses. In the Global Innovation Index (GII), the country has the 37th rank in the world in 2022 (WIPO, 2022), the highest in its history, and ranks 4th among the 36 upper-middle-income group economies. Turkiye's strongest pillar in the GII index is creative outputs, with a 15th rank in the globe, while the weakest pillar is institutions where it ranks as 101st.

Figure 1- The Seven GII Pillar Scores for Turkiye, 2022 (GEM)

As of 2023, Turkiye is an emerging innovator in the European Innovation Scoreboard, with a performance of 47.6% (European Commission, 2023). Compared to the EU average, it has lower per capita income, but a faster growing economy. Manufacturing has a larger share of the total employment, and the percentage of medium or high tech is lower (20.1% vs 30.8%), compared to

the EU average. Employment in services, on the other hand, has a lower share with a lower rate of knowledge-intensive services (20.2% vs 35.8%). In terms of enterprise births and total entrepreneurial activity, Türkiye performs quite well, 3.1% vs 1% and 15.7% vs 6.8% compared to the EU average respectively. However, top R&D spending enterprises and basic school entrepreneurial education & training add negatively to the innovation climate. Türkiye's R&D intensity ratio, as measured by R&D expenditures/GDP, was 1.13% in 2021¹, below the EU average of 2.27%². Community Innovation Survey³ (CIS) carried out by Turkish Statistical Institute shows that 38.5% of enterprises in Türkiye engaged in innovation activities between 2018-2020. This ratio was 42.5% in manufacturing industries but 33.5% in service industries.

Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Attitudes survey (2021)⁴ run by Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) exhibits interesting findings. While the perceived opportunities rate is 31.9 in Türkiye, compared to the global average of 54.8, entrepreneurial intentions rate surpasses the world average with a rate of 31.3 compared to 23.4. In addition, perceived capabilities and high job-creation expectations are higher than the global average, and fear of failure is lower. The results showcase the entrepreneurial spirit in the Turkish ecosystem, despite the low scores in some pillars of the entrepreneurial framework conditions.

Figure 2- Entrepreneurial Framework Conditions in Türkiye, 2021 (GEM)

Expert Ratings: 1 = highly insufficient, 5 = highly sufficient

As the hub of economic activities, Istanbul performs better than the country averages in R&D and innovation activities. It gets the highest share from the nation's R&D personnel with 27.3%, and approximately one fourth of R&D expenditures of the nation is made in Istanbul. In terms of innovative inputs and outputs, Istanbul gets the highest share in the country, followed by Ankara

¹ <https://data.oecd.org/rd/gross-domestic-spending-on-r-d.htm>

² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=R%26D_expenditure

³ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Innovation-Survey-2020-37457>

⁴ <https://www.gemconsortium.org/economy-profiles/turkey-2>

and İzmir (Kutgi & Işık Maden, 2020). According to WIPO's "World's Top 100 Science and Technology Clusters" 2022 report (WIPO, 2022), Istanbul has the 46th and Ankara has the 86th ranks among the S&T clusters in the world, both cities making notable jumps compared to the previous year.

The entrepreneurial ecosystem in Türkiye is an evolving landscape marked by a large and dynamic internal market, a well-developed physical infrastructure, government support, increasing collaboration among agents, and innovation. Despite facing challenges related to economic and financial instability, the Turkish startup environment has displayed a significant upwards in recent years. Young population, qualified universities, government policies and support schemes to encourage entrepreneurial and innovative activities, widening entrepreneurship education that promote cultural values appreciating entrepreneurial activities foster the entrepreneurship and innovation in the ecosystem. Support schemes developed by TÜBİTAK (Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye) and applied in collaboration with universities and other stakeholders in the ecosystems such as 1512 BİGG (Individual Young Entrepreneur) program play a pivotal role in connecting key stakeholders, improvement of the human capital in the ecosystem, the spread of entrepreneurial activities across the country and providing resources essential for startup creation and growth. With new initiatives and support policies the Turkish entrepreneurial ecosystem emerges as an attractive hub for both domestic and international entrepreneurs and investors.

France

France has a vibrant and diverse entrepreneurial ecosystem characterized by a mix of traditional and innovative industries. Overwhelmed by institutions and traditional thinking in government agencies, France still shows a vibrant growth of tech startups, some of them becoming European industry leaders. France's entrepreneurial ecosystem has become more dynamic in the last 4 years when the government has eased access to funding. Since Emmanuel Macron's first election as president in 2017, the number of business creations has continued to increase in France. While the PACTE law facilitates the creation of companies in France, it also promotes the in-depth modification of the French economic fabric.

Table 1 Business creation in France: The essentials (Source:GoToInvest)

Evolution of the number of business creations since 2017	68% increase
Articles of association of companies created in spring 2022	27.5% (Corporate), 12% (Corporate) and 60.5% (Micro-Enterprise)

Profiles of business start-ups in 2022	2/3 of companies are created to earn additional income or to create a job.
Most dynamic region in France in 2021	Île-de-France: +275,206 (+9% compared to 2020)
Least dynamic regions in France in 2021	Brittany and Normandy with 35,082 and 35,511 business creations.
Presence of women in French entrepreneurship in 2020	35% of business creations but more efficient (increase in turnover of 5.5% compared to 4.8%)

The French ecosystem is made up of more than 18,000 start-ups, over 370,000 employees, 240 incubators, and 50 accelerators . The number of self-entrepreneurs is 2.8 million in France., while 26% are micro-entrepreneurs, 40% have individual companies, 30% are owning their companies.- 63% are men , 37% are women-led businesses.⁵

Enjoying a diverse industrial base, and a growing culture of entrepreneurship, in 2010 France adopted the Investments for the Future Programme (PIA)⁶ aiming to stimulate employment, boost productivity and increase the competitiveness of French businesses by encouraging investment and innovation in priority sectors to drive growth. The French Tech 2030⁷ program was launched in 2012 to continue the commitments of the PIAs, with a total budget of €54 billion. While France tries to boost its tech entrepreneurial ecosystem, with the FrenchTech Program aiming to support high-potential technology companies, particularly in DeepTech, that are facing big challenges incurred by heavy bureaucratic business governance practices and a complicated institutional landscape, making it hard to seek for funding, especially at a scale-up phase. At the same time France constantly continues to attract innovators and start-ups from around the world, making it a significant player in the European and global entrepreneurial landscape. The entrepreneurial performance shows a growth compared to the global ecosystem overview by the Global Startup Ecosystem Index 2023 (Fig 1).

Fig 3. Global Startup Ecosystem Index- France, 2023

⁵ <https://www.startup-energy-transition.com/the-french-start-up-ecosystem-at-a-glance/>

⁶ <https://anr.fr/en/france-2030/france-2030/>

⁷ <https://lafrenchtech.com/en/how-france-helps-startups/french-tech-2030-en/?cn-reloaded=1>

France has known for around twenty years the continued progression of entrepreneurial activity. 2021 was once again a record year with nearly a million business creations. If this figure can be put into perspective due to the role of micro-entrepreneurship and in particular entrepreneurship linked to platforms, it nevertheless remains that all forms of business creation are experiencing positive developments. This dynamic can be explained by the contextual factors affecting entrepreneurial activity. The study carried out with experts from the entrepreneurial ecosystem (NES)⁸ makes it possible to reveal this potential and appreciate this favorable framework, notably through the context index national entrepreneur.

Fig 4. National Entrepreneurial Context Index (NECI score) (Source: NECI)

A more detailed analysis of the 13 indicators at the level of the 19 richest countries shows that France is average for 9 indicators. For one the position is more favorable and for three of them, she is very behind. French experts perceive government policies more favorably in terms of support and relevance (4/19).

France, for around forty years, is very committed to entrepreneurial support. The support also covers innovative entrepreneurship, with actions such as the French Tech, that entrepreneurship in a situation of poverty. These national policies are widely relayed at the local level through financing support systems or structures.

Fig 5. 13 indicators (Source: NES)

⁸ Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM France 2021-2022.) <https://gemconsortium.org/economy-profiles/france-62>

The **social enterprise landscape** in France is composed of a myriad of small organizations, with 64% having less than 5 employees and 75% having less than 10 employees. Only 1% has more than 250 employees in France have experienced an improvement in terms of gender equality over the last 15 years. This increase has been helped by the development of several initiatives, such as PAR (Plan d'Action Regional – Regional Action Plan), the creation of support for business development, and initiatives to enable access to finance. Today, women represent 40% of sole proprietorships, 40% of micro-entrepreneurs, 37% of individual entrepreneurs (excluding micro-enterprises), 25% of the managers of SARL (Société à Responsabilité Limitée – private limited liability companies) and 17% of salaried company directors (excluding SARLs), and 27% of French women are or have been in an entrepreneurial process (INSEE, 2015⁹). However, the national trend is different from the regional statistics.

Fig 6 Engagement for entrepreneurship by women and men.

The proportion of women in entrepreneurship has increased with microenterprise status. They account for **35%** of sole proprietorships. However, this figure has been stable since 2015. Women are therefore not creating more businesses under President Macron. However, they benefit from a support system that is as important as that of men (Action'elles, FNCIDFF, the Agency for Women's

⁹OECD Entrepreneurship at a Glance, 2016, <https://www.oecd.org/sdd/business-stats/EaG-France-Eng.pdf>

Entrepreneurship, Les Premières, Force Femmes, etc.).

Within companies, on the other hand, France is at the top of the European ranking for the presence of women on the boards of directors of CAC 40 companies since the Copé-Zimmermann law that imposes them (voted in 2011). Women are working in the sectors of activity where the number of start-ups is the highest: health, social work, household, industry and education.

Ireland

An important document that we consider as must-read is the Irish government report of the SME Taskforce on 'National SME and Entrepreneurship Growth Plan'; though published in August 2021 and at a time that the Corona pandemic was still shocking jobs, employment and – not only - the Irish economy, it included recommendations and calls for actions that are highly relevant especially as economies in EU and globally continue to face challenges so there is an imperative need for being fit to face continuous challenges.

There appears to be a widespread consensus that the Irish entrepreneurial and business ecosystem is in a strong position. This dates back to the times of the 'Celtic Tiger' (in Irish: An Tíogar Ceilteach), a term that has been used to refer to the economy of Ireland from the mid-1990s to the late 2000s, a period of rapid real economic growth fuelled by foreign direct investment. The boom was, regrettably but perhaps unsurprisingly, dampened by a subsequent property bubble which resulted in a severe economic downturn.

According to Professor Roy Foster¹⁰, the cause for the success was a combination of 'a new sense of initiative' and factors such as low taxation, pro-business regulatory policies, and a young, tech-savvy workforce. All in all, all these factors still persist and contribute to the country's success story.

What is important in the context of the ExcellEnt project are *not* the incentives of many multinational corporations such as Intel or Google whose decision to do business in Ireland is due to generous incentives from the Irish Industrial Development Authority, but *the collective understanding in the Irish society of entrepreneurship as an individual person's or a group's creative capacity to identify an opportunity and pursue it in order to produce new value or economic success.*

This is something that, according to our opinion, places the Irish entrepreneurial skill in a privileged position with respect to other countries in the EU and it is for this reason that Ireland shall continue to keep a unique position within the European entrepreneurship scene.

¹⁰ R. F. Foster (2008) Luck and the Irish: A Brief History of Change c. 1970-2000, Oxford University Press.

Ukraine

Entrepreneurship plays a pivotal role in Ukraine's economic landscape, serving as a driving force for innovation, job creation, and economic growth. SMEs are drivers of all positive processes that take place in the economy of developed countries, and make a significant contribution to social progress and are the basis of sustainable economic growth.

This especially applies to modern business conditions in Ukraine, where SMEs are the leading sector of the market economy. They contribute to increasing the competitiveness of the products of the national economy, ensure the growth of the gross domestic product, saturate the domestic product market, expand the sphere of employment of the population and contribute to the economic and social development of the country. That is why small entrepreneurship plays an important role in ensuring the country's competitiveness on the world market and is one of the priorities of the state regulatory policy of Ukraine, which should promote the development of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship as a driving force for the economic growth of the national economy.

Nowadays the Ukrainian entrepreneurial ecosystem faces various challenges due to Russia's full-scale invasion against Ukraine. Nevertheless, since the beginning of the invasion, Ukrainian entrepreneurs have shown remarkable resilience and creativity. They play a crucial role in diversifying the country's economy, particularly in sectors like technology, agriculture, and renewable energy.

- Key characteristics, geographical locations, and main stakeholders involved.

Greece

Geographical location

Greece, located in southeastern Europe, sits at the crossroads of Europe, Asia, and Africa. With its diverse landscapes that include islands, mountains, and fertile plains, the nation boasts a strategic maritime position in the Mediterranean Sea. The country shares land borders with Albania, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, and Turkey. The Aegean Sea lies to the east of mainland Greece, while the Ionian Sea lies to the west, both parts of the larger Mediterranean basin.

Several key cities and regions in Greece have risen as pivotal points for entrepreneurial activities:

Athens (Attica): As Greece's capital and its most populous city, Athens is the epicentre of business innovation and entrepreneurial fervor. It houses a multitude of startups, coworking spaces, innovation hubs, and venture capital firms. Institutions such as the National Technical University of Athens [2] and Athens University of Economics and Business [3] frequently engage with the city's bustling startup ecosystem, synergizing academic prowess with entrepreneurial initiative.

Thessaloniki (Central Macedonia): Being Greece's second-largest city, Thessaloniki is both a significant economic hub and a vibrant cultural centre. Thessaloniki's entrepreneurial spirit thrives on its youthful demographic and the influential presence of institutions like the Aristotle University [4]. A key highlight in Thessaloniki's entrepreneurial calendar is the Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF) [5]. This annual event is not only a platform for business exchanges but has, over the years, evolved into a significant venue for startups, innovation showcases, and tech talks. The fair strengthens Thessaloniki's reputation as a beacon for business and entrepreneurship in the region.

Thessaly: This central Greek region, with cities like Larissa and Volos, is becoming increasingly recognized for its agricultural innovation. Leveraging its vast plains, which are among the most fertile in Greece, Thessaly has seen a surge in agritech startups and sustainable farming initiatives. The region also benefits from the academic input of the University of Thessaly [6], promoting research and innovation in various sectors.

Thrace: Located at the northeastern tip of Greece, the region's proximity to the Turkish border makes it strategically important. Alexandroupolis, its capital, is emerging as a hub for logistics and trade-based startups.

Aegean Islands: Popular tourist destinations like Mykonos and Santorini have witnessed a surge in eco-tourism and luxury tourism-based startups, leveraging the region's natural beauty and cultural heritage.

Crete: Heraklion, with the Science and Technology Park of Crete [7], has championed tech-driven enterprises. The island's rich history and cultural heritage also make it ripe for innovative tourism and cultural ventures.

- This diverse geographical distribution underscores Greece's varied entrepreneurial potential. Each region, with its unique strengths and characteristics, contributes to the rich tapestry of Greek business innovation.

Key Stakeholders

Entrepreneurs and Startups: The lifeblood of the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem, entrepreneurs and startups are the originators of innovation. They bring fresh ideas to life, creating products, services, and technologies that have the potential to impact society and the economy at large. According to Elevate Greece [9], 768 Startups are currently registered in the Greek Ecosystem, 12 of which perform activities in the Region of Thessaly.

Incubators and Accelerators: Incubators nurture startups during their nascent stages, providing essential resources such as office infrastructure, mentor networks, and consultation services. Accelerators, on the other hand, offer intensive educational programs aimed at propelling startups from ideation to product development and market readiness. Though similar in objective, their approaches and timelines vary.

Academic Bodies and Research Institutions: Greece is home to 24 state-accredited universities [10], each a hub of research and academic excellence. Among them, the University of Thessaly [6] stands as a cornerstone in the Region of Thessaly, fostering innovation and contributing significantly to the local startup ecosystem. Greek universities offer a broad range of disciplines, from humanities and social sciences to health sciences and technology. Advanced educational opportunities are also abundant, with one- to two-year master's programs and doctoral research options.

In the bustling panorama of Greece's innovation ecosystem, research institutions stand as pivotal key stakeholders, functioning as epicentres of knowledge, innovation, and technological advancements. They not only offer robust platforms for research and development but also act as critical interfaces between academia, industry, and government policies. From "Athena" Research and Innovation Centre [11] to the National Centre of Scientific Research "Demokritos" [12], these institutes span a broad spectrum of disciplines, including ICT, biomedical sciences, energy, and more.

Federations and Business Associations: Federations and business associations are the advocacy arm of the entrepreneurial community. They offer services like advice, financial expertise, and governmental lobbying, aiming to create a favourable business environment for their members.

Government Agencies: A quintet of ministries plays crucial roles in fostering the Greek Innovation Ecosystem. The Ministry of Development and Investments [13] and the Ministry of Digital Governance [14] mainly focus on business growth and digital infrastructure. Meanwhile, the Ministry of Rural Development and Food [15], the Ministry of Environment and Energy [16], and the Ministry of Health [17] each bring sector-specific support, funding, and policies to the table. Lastly,

the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs [18] embeds entrepreneurial education into academia, thereby cultivating future innovators.

Each of these stakeholders brings a unique set of resources, expertise, and perspectives to the table, contributing to a multifaceted and dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem in Greece. Together, they create a rich tapestry of support, funding, and innovation that enables Greek startups to not just survive but to thrive.

Bulgaria

Geographical Location

Bulgaria boasts a strategic geographical position at the crossroads of three continents: Europe, Asia, and Africa. Bordered by Greece and Turkey to the south, Serbia and North Macedonia to the west, and Romania to the north, and nestled along the coast of the Black Sea to the east, it serves as a vital gateway for both maritime and overland trade routes. Furthermore, the Danube River, flowing along its northern boundary with Romania, enhances its significance as a major transport pathway, connecting various European nations and facilitating trade and commerce.

Several key cities and regions in Bulgaria have emerged as central hubs for entrepreneurial endeavors:

Sofia: As the capital and largest city of Bulgaria, Sofia stands as the primary hub for startups and entrepreneurial activities. The cityscape is dotted with tech parks, coworking spaces, and innovation centres, with many major tech companies and international corporations choosing Sofia as their base. The city is home to Sofia Tech Park, a major innovation centre that fosters collaboration between academia, business, and government. Events like "DigitalK" [2] and "Webit.Festival" [3] further cement its reputation as a tech and startup hotspot. Central to Sofia's entrepreneurial spirit are its educational institutions. Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" and the Technical University of Sofia are pivotal, fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, and producing a steady stream of tech-savvy graduates ready to make their mark in the business world.

Plovdiv: Often referred to as the cultural capital, Plovdiv is rapidly carving out a reputation for its tech and startup scene. The city's growth in the IT sector is evident, with an increasing number of startups and technology parks. The Plovdiv Innovation Hub serves as a focal point for tech enthusiasts, startups, and investors.

Varna: Situated on the picturesque Black Sea coast, Varna is more than just a tourist hotspot; it's an emerging tech hub. The Varna Innovation Hub and the annual "Innowave Summit" [4] are testament to the city's growing significance in the tech and startup landscape. Universities offering tech and business courses, such as the Technical University of Varna and Varna Free University "Chernorizets Hrabar", have led to a burgeoning number of tech startups in the city. These initiatives and institutions make Varna a significant player in Bulgaria's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Burgas: With its strategic port and logistical advantages at the coast of the Black Sea, Burgas is evolving as a significant entrepreneurial centre. The city attracts a diverse range of businesses, from tourism, trade and logistics to manufacturing. The city's Burgas IT Pro Meetup events [5] and the establishment of the Burgas Business Incubator [6] underscore its commitment to fostering innovation and entrepreneurship. Burgas Free University and the Technical University of Burgas play a pivotal role in this growth, nurturing tech talent and promoting research-driven entrepreneurial initiatives.

Stara Zagora: Located in the heart of Bulgaria, Stara Zagora is a vital economic hub with a diversified economy spanning manufacturing, agriculture, and services. The city's entrepreneurial spirit is further fuelled by Trakia University. With faculties focusing on technology and business, the university is a beacon of innovation and entrepreneurship, ensuring Stara Zagora remains a key player in Bulgaria's business landscape.

Ruse: Nestled on the banks of the Danube River, Ruse is both a significant economic and cultural centre. Its proximity to the Romanian border makes it a pivotal point for cross-border trade and business. The Ruse Free Zone [7], offering favourable conditions for businesses, underlines the city's growing prominence in the entrepreneurial landscape. The University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev" remains a significant institution, fostering an environment of learning and innovation.

These cities and regions have not only shown growth in traditional sectors but have also embraced the new age of digital transformation, making them pivotal points for entrepreneurial activities in Bulgaria.

Historical Background

Tracing back to its rich trading traditions during the medieval period, Bulgaria has always had a deep-rooted entrepreneurial spirit [8]. Bulgaria's entrepreneurial landscape has undergone significant evolution, especially in the context of its journey towards and after its accession to the

European Union. The late 1980s marked a shift in the economic structure, setting the stage for the entrepreneurial activities that would flourish in the subsequent decades [8]. The global entrepreneurial culture, combined with local initiatives, has positioned Sofia as one of the top cities for starting a business, as recognized by Forbes and StartupBlink's "Global Startup Ecosystems Index" [9] ranking. The establishment of funds like Eleven Ventures [10] and LAUNCHub [11] in 2012 provided a significant boost to the entrepreneurial culture, especially among the younger generation. These funds, along with the emergence of successful entrepreneurs such as Vasil Terziev, Svetozar Georgiev, and Ivaylo Penchev, have played a pivotal role in shaping the ecosystem. These entrepreneurs have not only achieved success in their ventures but have also become inspiring role models and mentors for budding entrepreneurs in the country.

Furthermore, the development of entrepreneurial culture in Bulgaria has been complemented by educational initiatives. Institutions like Sofia University have been at the forefront, introducing entrepreneurship-focused programs and collaborating with various entities to promote entrepreneurial education. Events like the European Day of the Entrepreneur [12] have become annual fixtures, celebrating and fostering the spirit of entrepreneurship in the country.

Turkiye

Geographical Location

Turkiye, a transcontinental country located partly in Europe and partly in Asia, bridges East to West and South to the North. It has land borders with Greece, Bulgaria, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, and Syria. Surrounded by the Mediterranean Sea on the south, Aegean Sea on the west and the Black Sea on the North, the country also bridges Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, and Russia to the open seas through its two Bosphorus. With a landscape including islands, mountains, and fertile plains scattered on a land area of 783,562 km², Turkiye is not only a geographical bridge but has a unique geopolitical, commercial, and cultural position.

Istanbul: Located at the intersection of Europe and Asia and having land on both continents, Istanbul is Turkiye's most populated city with its 16 million citizens. It serves as the economic and financial centre with the highest share in total GDP (30.4% in 2021), as well as highest contribution to the GDP in various industries except for agriculture and other services (TUIK, 2022). The city has the second highest GDP per capita (Usd 15,666 in 2021) following Kocaeli. Istanbul hosts fifty-seven universities including highly prestigious institutions such as Boğaziçi University, Sabancı University,

Koç University, Istanbul Technical University, and Yıldız Technical University, which serve as catalysts to the entrepreneurship ecosystem. A multitude of business incubators, coworking spaces, and venture capital firms are also located in Istanbul, along with several techno parks and technology transfer offices. The city has three main ports, four free trade zones, and two international airports. Istanbul is the eighth most visited city in the world. Thanks to its geographic location, as well as its dynamic habitat and cosmopolitan structure, it is gaining a bigger proportion of international commerce every year.

Ankara: Geographically located in the middle of the country, Ankara is the capital of Türkiye and is the second most populated city with a 5.8 Mio population. The city accounts for 9.2% of economic activity in the country and is the second biggest Science and Technology hub in Türkiye. Ankara hosts 21 universities including prestigious institutions worldwide such as Middle East Technical University (ODTÜ) and İhsan Doğramacı Bilkent University. With a multitude of innovation hubs, incubators, techno parks, and technology transfer offices, Ankara is a rising star in the Turkish and global entrepreneurship ecosystem.

İzmir: İzmir is Türkiye's third largest city with a 4.5 Mio population and has a 6.4% share in the country's economic activity. It is a port city in the Eastern Mediterranean, located on the Western coast of Türkiye with a coastline of 629 km. With 9 universities, 4 technology development zones, 97 R&D centres accompanied by its startup incubators and investors, İzmir is the third largest innovation and entrepreneurship hub in Türkiye. It gets a balanced share in the country's different economic sectors and has high potential for blue growth. İzmir Development Agency (İZKA) has announced a blue growth strategy, as well as a green growth strategy, that puts the maritime transportation and port services to the centre to reinforce the position of İzmir ports in the Mediterranean freight and passenger traffic. Fishing and marine life, ship-recycling, coastal tourism, blue startups, blue energy, blue investments, and maritime protection are targeted areas to further boost the economic growth¹¹.

Bursa: The fourth most populated city with 3.2 Mio residents and the fifth largest economic activity with 4.2% of GDP contribution, Bursa, is located at the South of Marmara Sea and is only 1,5-hour drive to Istanbul and 1 hour drive to Kocaeli. Historically famous as Green Bursa, with its plains and mountain forests, it is now an industrial hub that sits at the heart of automotive and textile industries both in Türkiye and the world. Furniture, machinery, and agriculture also have considerable shares in the economic activity, while the local development agency recently targets at

¹¹ <https://izka.org.tr/innovation-and-entrepreneurship/?lang=en>

empowering the e-commerce potential of the city¹². Bursa carries the advantages of geographic proximity to key locations, marine transport for exports, and a skilled workforce. It hosts three universities, 3 incubators, 2 technology development zones, one free trade zone, and one technology transfer office.

Kocaeli: Kocaeli is the ninth largest city with 2 Mio population but has the fifth place in economic activity with 4.3%, as well as the highest GDP per capita (Usd 17,089 in 2021) in Turkiye. Also located by the Marmara Sea, it has borders with Istanbul, from where many professionals travel for work. It is an industrial and trade hub with chemistry, automotive and iron-steel as the leading sectors, and has intense trade activity from its ports. Kocaeli hosts 2 universities, 4 technology development zones, 1 free trade zone, and 3 technology transfer offices. Bilişim Vadisi (Informatics Valley)¹³ and Tubitak (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkiye)¹⁴ are in Kocaeli, boosting both the region's and country's innovation potential.

¹² <https://bursainvest.gov.tr/page/2/>

¹³ <https://bilisimvadisi.com.tr/en>

¹⁴ <https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en>

Figure 7- Share of the first 5 cities with the highest share in GDP by economic activity, 2021(TUIK)

Historical Background

Türkiye is heir to several great civilizations' historical heritage such as The Hittite, Lydian, Persian, Roman, Byzantine, Seljuk, and the Ottoman Empire. After centuries of dominance on three continents, The Ottoman Empire started to lose power by the end of the 17th century. Falling behind the Western countries in intellectual and technological development, its weakened military losing several wars, and the nations under its control declaring wars for their independence, the Empire dissolved in terms of territory, as well as becoming economically dependent on foreign countries. After being defeated in World War I, its territory was partitioned among the Allies, leaving a small Turkish territory. In 1923, the Turkish War of Independence was won, and the Treaty of Lausanne determined the borders of the country, followed by the establishment of the Republic of Türkiye on 29th Oct 1923.

The new Republic was a poor country with eroded physical and social capital. While the state emphasized industrialization and initiated the efforts in the republic's first 3 decades, after 1950, this was replaced with a new policy emphasizing agriculture-led growth in line with the Marshall Plan of the U.S. (Pamuk, 2010). In 1960, Türkiye saw a coup d'état based on the fear of the military on threatened secularity in the country, and at the same period, import substitution industrialization became the new economic policy. In 1980, the country saw another coup d'état following internal tensions due to the economic crisis and the left-right movements. The economic liberalisation policy, set just before the coup with the IMF and WB, remained unchanged and regulations on export

subsidies, privatisation, free exchange circulation and open financial markets increasingly followed. The country was fully integrated into the Customs Union in 1996 and became a member of WTO in 1997. In 1999, Türkiye was recognized as a candidate state for full membership to the EU. Since the negotiations started in 2005, several legislations have been changed and new institutions have been established regarding the economy, health, environment, and civil rights.

France

Geographical Location

France is a Western European country known for its central location on the continent. It shares borders with several countries, including Germany, Italy, Spain, Belgium, Luxembourg, Switzerland, and Monaco. To the west, it is bordered by the Atlantic Ocean, and to the south, it has a Mediterranean coastline along the Mediterranean Sea. This strategic position makes France a vital crossroads for trade and cultural exchange within Europe and a gateway to both Western and Southern Europe. France's entrepreneurial landscape is diverse and spread across various regions and cities, with startup hubs created in major regions. While entrepreneurial activity can be found throughout the country, some regions and cities are particularly noteworthy for their contribution to France's thriving start-up and innovation ecosystem. **France boats a vibrant startup scene ranking 4th in Europe and 8th within the competitive global top 10** . Although Paris serving as a natural concentration of capital a talent due to its capital status, about 25% of startups are created in other regions of France every year². Continuous efforts of the French government to boost entrepreneurial culture and provide financial and infrastructural support to tech startups brought an outstanding result of 1 061 969 companies³ set up in 2022 (almost a 2% increase from 2021, and a new record).

According to Ernst&Young's 2023 France Attractiveness Survey⁴, for four consecutive years it remains the most attractive European country for FDI projects, with almost half of them in rural or small city areas. France enjoys diverse qualified human capital necessary for tech projects across the country.

Paris has Silicon Sentier (**Sentier du Silicon**), located in the 2nd and 3rd districts of Paris, often referred to as the French Silicon Valley. This place initiated the rapid development of the French Tech ecosystem, becoming home to numerous start-ups, tech incubators, accelerators, and co-working spaces. Iconic

Station F, opened in 2017 as a French tech flagship, has become one of the world's largest start-up campuses. Station F hosts 1000 startups every year, acting as a hub for entrepreneurship, innovation, and networking. Thirty three acceleration programs, each of them focused on one vertical, are operated there.

Paris&Co was launched as an incubator and accelerator network for Paris. Paris&Co supports start-ups in various industries, including technology, fashion, and sustainability, focusing on a soft landing 4-week program, helping startups create businesses in Paris. To the south of Paris **Plateau de Saclay is situated**. It is a flagship project in Greater Paris. The Paris-Saclay cluster is the driver for the renewal of French and European industry. Inspired by the success of Silicon Valley, the ambitious scientific and technological cluster project was set up on the Saclay plateau. Its three main components are: presence of leading French industrial players, research labs, and business incubation facilities. It is often referred to as the Silicon Valley of Europe. Plateau de Saclay hosts research centers from most of CAC 40 Companies and public research institutions as Centre pour l'Énergie Atomique (CEA) | Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IPP), HEC and Université Paris Saclay ranked first university in Europe, and 15th in the world⁵.

Lyon, France's second largest and second richest metropolitan area, has invested both capital and human talent to become France's first smart connected city. Three digital clusters, Digital League (software and digital services), I-Care (e-health) and Cluster Lumière (light technology) contribute to creating 42 700 jobs.

H7, a collaborative workspace and innovation Lyon hub that fosters entrepreneurship and creativity in the region, has hosted 70 and supported 160 start-ups since 2019.

The **Aix-Marseille** region, an international logistics hub, is now known for its diverse entrepreneurship ecosystem, with a focus on digital innovation and sustainability. This focus has brought it €10 billion annual turnover in new digital economy, which employs 49 000 people.

Toulouse, famous for its **Aerospace Valley**, is a major hub for the aerospace and aviation industry. Aerospace Valley is a cluster of businesses, research centres, and start-ups driving innovation in this sector, which in 2022 supported 128 projects, helping attract €55 million of public funds into 55.

Nantes is recognized for its strong focus on digital innovation and creative industries, hosting Lydia, a fintech market disruptor, OpenClassrooms, an edtech emerging leader, and others. It is home to several start-up incubators and accelerators, such as Nantes CityLab, that provides physical and

digital infrastructure to help innovators test new solutions in real life, but it was one of the other active participants of the FrenchTech Program.

Nice is a successful example of tech regional diversity in France. Not only it is linked to **Sophia Antipolis**, a technology park, which is home to 2500 companies with a total value of €5,6 billion euros, but it excels in attracting industry leaders, e.g. Mercedes relocated its Design Studio from Italy to Nice in 2019, due to its attractive regional government investment and tech climate and qualified educated workforce.

These regions and cities play a crucial role in France's entrepreneurial landscape, offering a supportive infrastructure, access to funding, and a network of like-minded entrepreneurs. They contribute significantly to the country's reputation as a hub for innovation and start-up growth in Europe.

Historical Background

The historical background of entrepreneurship in France is rich and complex, reflecting centuries of economic, social, and political evolution. The country has developed its entrepreneurial culture from Medieval Guilds to contemporary focused development of regional innovation hubs.

The Age of Colonial Exploration boosted trade and commerce, and the country developed manufacturing and learned how to work with exotic materials. Entrepreneurial and innovative individuals were crucial in these endeavors. Versailles Palace, built by French King Louis XIV made France a reference for Culture and Luxury manufacturing. And France still keeps leadership in Luxury design and manufacturing industries.

France's history of entrepreneurship reflects its adaptability and resilience, evolving over centuries to encompass a diverse range of industries and business models. Today, France is a prominent player in the global entrepreneurial landscape, contributing to innovation and economic development across various sectors.

For the last 20 years France saw a surge in technological innovation and entrepreneurship in the late. The establishment of high-tech hubs, research centres, and business incubators contributed to the growth of start-ups in fields like information technology, biotechnology, and aerospace. Building up on its rich entrepreneurial traditions The French government has actively promoted entrepreneurship through various policies and initiatives. Programs like the "Auto-Entrepreneur"

status and tax incentives aim to support small businesses and start-ups, and later on under Francois Hollande Presidency, starting French tech as a brand and as a Program

France continues to foster entrepreneurship through a dynamic start-up ecosystem, with cities like Paris being recognized as hubs for innovation. The country has also embraced sustainable entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship as key drivers of economic growth.

Ireland

Geographical Location

In contrast to Germany that is located in the centre of Europe, Ireland is at Europe's western periphery. However, Ireland enjoys long-standing and deeply and successfully rooted relations and access to both the UK and North America (both U.S.A. and Canada). Due to this reason, the Irish economy was proven resilient enough to have emerged strongly from the recent global recession with the highest growth and population rates in the European Union.

In the late 1980s, Ireland was still classified as a 'cohesion country' in need of structural funds. A generation on, Ireland is a net contributor to the EU budget, a hub of global business and Europe's fastest growing economy. Exports of goods and services as a proportion of GDP rose from 24% in 1965

to 124% in 2015, making Ireland the fifth most intensive exporter of its goods and services in the world.

Ireland's outward investment matches Foreign Direct Investment and Irish companies employ as many people in the USA as US companies employ in Ireland. Ireland is the world's second largest software exporter.

Historical Background

It is difficult and by definition set on a wrong track to consider one country as unique for its development. However, it is important to identify the path that brings some countries or regions to excel and go to the details of detecting the contributing factors. So in this respect we can risk to reverse the quote that comes from the first sentence of Tolstoy's Anna Karenina according to which 'happy families are all alike but every unhappy family is unhappy in its own way': there can be many success stories regarding nations and countries that support innovation and entrepreneurship in

their own all different ways, and same applies also for failure stories. However, regarding innovation and entrepreneurship what counts most is to provide a non-volatile i.e. stable environment that builds trust to all types of stakeholders, namely not only the entrepreneurs themselves but also investors and last but not least the employees and the labor force that will be needed to implement the innovations and execute the entrepreneurial agenda.

The Irish people have always been known for their creativity and inventiveness. This is evident in the many inventions that have come out of Ireland over the years, such as colour photography, guided missiles or the modern tractor. This creative spirit can be traced back to ancient times when Irish monks were responsible for preserving much of Western civilisation's knowledge during Europe's Dark Ages. However, all other participating 'ecosystems' from the other countries of the ExcellEnt project can brag about similar qualities. *In our opinion, one important differentiation factor comes from the willingness of government and administration authorities like Enterprise Ireland to walk the extra mile and find solutions that will make things work.* This is something that cannot be found in other countries as widely openly and freely available, and this is also the reason why researchers and scientists find it easier to build their own enterprise in Ireland than in other countries of the EU.

Ukraine

Geographical Location

Ukraine is one of the largest untapped emerging economies in Europe. The country had about 42 million inhabitants before the Russian full-scale invasion. It had access to markets in Central Asia, the Middle East, and beyond. According to the UN, as of 2023 the population of Ukraine has decreased up to 37 mln people, as caused by the ongoing refugee crisis and loss of territory¹⁵.

With the war conflict of 2014 and full-scale invasion of 2022 global changes have taken place in the business attractiveness of the territories of Ukraine - first losing powerful facilities in the eastern part of the country and Crimea, followed by further occupation of eastern and southern territories (in total 19% of the territory of the country) and endangering more in the frontier state.

¹⁵ «UkrainePopulation(2023)», Worldometer, <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/ukraine-population/> (accessed September 25, 2023).

As of today the positions of the north-eastern and southern regions, where hostilities took place/are taking place, are deteriorating, while the western regions have the opposite trend¹⁶.

The regions that now account for the majority of entrepreneurial activity are:

- Kyiv. The capital retains its leadership in absolute numbers, but the 3-year dynamics of business development in Kyiv and Lviv Oblast suggest that the capital has begun to lose its dominant position, and other regions with a more attractive business climate successfully compete with it;
- Lviv and Kyiv regions;
- Central and western regions (emerging);
- Regions known for the most active entrepreneurial activities (Odessa, Kharkiv, Zaporizhzhia) have drastically lost their positions within the last 1.5 years;

In addition to the obvious reasons for such changes, the geographical location, the local business climate, and other factors manifested during the pandemic, the important factors are: integration of internally displaced persons into communities and their involvement in economic development, effectiveness of interactions between military administrations and territorial communities, adaptation of local programs and business support tools, ability to support export development, among others¹⁷.

Historical Background

In 1991, Ukraine gained independence after the dissolution of the USSR. During the 1990s, Ukraine faced challenges due to its post-socialist economy. Despite enduring a challenging period of transformation, Ukraine continued to face a lack of peace and stability. The 2004 Orange Revolution and subsequent protests in 2013 were not entirely successful in meeting expectations. In 2014, a war with Russia erupted, resulting in the annexation of Crimea and eastern regions of Ukraine. This conflict escalated significantly in 2022 when Russia launched a massive offensive, causing colossal damage and many deaths.

The entrepreneurship in independent Ukraine began with privatization and removal of legal restrictions on the entrepreneurial activity. The post-Soviet conditions for the development of

¹⁶ «Війна та регіони України: як змінюється привабливість для підприємців - аналітика», <https://decentralization.gov.ua/news/14970>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

¹⁷ Ibidem.

entrepreneurship contributed to the formation of a type of big business (financial and industrial groups) merged with state power. The introduction of the hryvnia in 1996, stabilization of the financial sector, establishment of foreign economic relations, and economic growth after 2000 contributed to the formation of small and medium-sized enterprises. The "Orange Revolution" of 2004 proved the presence of a stratum of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs with their own priorities¹⁸.

¹⁸ «Підприємництво в незалежній Україні», Вікіпедія,
https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Підприємництво_в_Україні#Підприємництво_в_незалежній_Україні,
(accessed September 25, 2023).

SWOT Analysis

- Detailed SWOT analysis for each entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Greece

This section provides a detailed SWOT analysis of the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem, evaluating its Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. This comprehensive analysis aims to capture the range of factors that contribute to the ecosystem's development, growth, and competitiveness. The insights have been summarized for quick reference in a SWOT Matrix, depicted in Figure 1. The analysis serves to identify crucial areas for development, existing limitations, and potential risks and opportunities that could influence the ecosystem's future.

Figure 8: SWOT Matrix showcasing the key factors shaping Greece's entrepreneurial landscape

Strengths

Highly Educated Talent Pool: One of the most significant assets of the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem is its highly educated workforce, particularly in fields like IT, engineering, healthcare, and social sciences. According to OECD [23], 44.20% of the young adult population in Greece has a tertiary education. This level of educational attainment positions Greece competitively in terms of human capital, which is crucial for any startup ecosystem. Skilled professionals contribute to innovation and technological advancements, key drivers for a startup's success.

Supportive Infrastructure: Coworking spaces and innovation hubs like JOIST [20] serve as nurturing grounds for startups. These spaces provide entrepreneurs with the essential infrastructure they need to grow their ideas, from office amenities to networking opportunities. Supportive environments like these facilitate collaboration and the exchange of ideas, creating a vibrant community that nurtures entrepreneurship.

Government Initiatives: The Greek government has shown commitment to easing business regulations. Recent improvements include reduced time to register a company and eliminated requirements for tax clearance. These policy shifts are instrumental in creating a more business-friendly environment, albeit with room for further improvement, as evidenced by Greece's ranking in the World Bank's Doing Business 2020 report [24].

Collaborative Networks: The entrepreneurial culture in Greece is highly collaborative, characterized by strong networks that span academia, industry, and governmental bodies. Events like the Innovent Forum [26] and platforms such as Elevate Greece [1] help facilitate such collaborations, which in turn attract funding and additional resources for startups. This symbiosis among various stakeholders not only encourages knowledge dissemination but also fortifies the ecosystem.

International Exposure: Many Greek students opt for higher education abroad, returning to the country with not just advanced skills but also international exposure and a global perspective. This diversity enriches the talent pool, making it more adaptable and better suited to the rapidly evolving demands of the startup world.

These strengths collectively contribute to making the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem more robust and competitive. They create a synergy that not only propels individual startups but also elevates the entire ecosystem, attracting both domestic and international attention.

Weaknesses

Bureaucratic Hurdles: One of the most significant barriers for startups in Greece is the bureaucratic complexity that often accompanies business operations. Despite strides made by the government to simplify the regulatory framework, the country still ranks 79th in the World Bank's Doing Business 2020 report [24]. These bureaucratic challenges can delay business operations, deter potential entrepreneurs, and ultimately affect the growth of the startup ecosystem.

Limited Access to Early-Stage Funding: Although Greece has various funding mechanisms, such as venture capital, angel investors, and public funding programs, securing early-stage funding remains a significant challenge for startups. The local venture capital ecosystem is relatively nascent, especially when compared to more developed startup landscapes like the UK, Germany, or France, which boast a much more vibrant funding environment. Additionally, existing public and private investment initiatives often prioritize more mature and less risky ventures. As a result, startups in their early stages find themselves with limited options for seed and pre-seed funding, constraining their ability to turn innovative ideas into scalable businesses. This shortfall in early-stage financing is a key limitation that hampers the overall growth prospects of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Greece.

Small Size of Domestic Market: The size of the domestic market in Greece poses inherent limitations for startups with ambitions of rapid growth and scalability. One of the defining features is Greece's population, which stands at approximately 10 million, inherently limiting the consumer base that startups can tap into for local growth. Coupled with this is the country's GDP, which is substantially smaller compared to larger European economies, thereby limiting the market size and making it less appealing for substantial venture capital investments. Additionally, the average purchasing power of consumers isn't as high as in some other European countries, further constraining the revenue streams for new businesses.

Due to these factors, startups in Greece often find the domestic market restrictive for achieving scalable growth. This situation not only limits their revenue potential but can also dissuade venture capital firms from investing, as they typically seek opportunities that promise larger returns. As a result, Greek startups often have to look beyond their borders to achieve meaningful scale. While international expansion comes with its own set of challenges, such as adapting to different markets, cultures, and regulations, it often becomes a necessary strategy for growth given the constraints of the domestic market.

Relatively High Corporate Tax Rate: Greece has a corporate tax rate of 22%, which is slightly above the EU average of 21.5%. While the difference may seem negligible, it adds another layer of financial burden for startups. Combined with other bureaucratic complexities, this slight disadvantage can influence the decision-making process of both domestic and international entrepreneurs contemplating starting a business in Greece.

To overcome these weaknesses, there is a need for more streamlined regulatory processes and easier access to funding, especially at the early stages. Increasing collaborations with international entities could also provide startups with the market access they need to scale. The government can also consider tax incentives or subsidies specifically targeted at startups to offset the slightly higher corporate tax rates.

These weaknesses, if not addressed, could slow down the development and competitiveness of the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem. Therefore, targeted interventions in these areas are crucial for fortifying the ecosystem's growth and stability.

Opportunities

High Potential in Emerging Sectors: Emerging industries like eHealth, EduTech, and AgriTech present significant opportunities for Greek startups. These sectors are increasingly benefiting from technological innovations and are poised for growth, offering a fertile ground for startups to develop innovative solutions. The already highly skilled talent pool in healthcare, social sciences, and technology can be leveraged to fuel growth in these industries.

Access to the EU's Expansive Single Market: Being a member of the European Union, Greece enjoys the advantage of having access to a single, expansive market with standardized regulations. This access offers Greek startups the potential to scale quickly across multiple countries without the need for region-specific adaptations. The EU also offers various funding programs that Greek startups can tap into, further enhancing their growth prospects.

Capability to Leverage Technological Advancements: The country's strong emphasis on education, especially in IT and engineering, gives Greek startups the technical know-how to adapt quickly to technological advancements. This adaptability could prove advantageous, especially in rapidly evolving fields like Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, and Internet of Things, thereby offering more avenues for growth.

Opportunities for Public-Private Partnerships: In recent years, the Greek government has actively shown a willingness to collaborate with the private sector to boost innovation and entrepreneurship. A prime example of this is the "Research-Create-Innovate" initiative [27]. This action is specifically designed to link research and innovation with entrepreneurship, aiming to enhance the competitiveness, productivity, and global orientation of Greek enterprises, particularly SMEs. By channelling resources efficiently, the program encourages the application of innovative solutions within the business sector. Such public-private partnerships can bring in additional resources, both in terms of funding and expertise. This is particularly beneficial for startups operating in sectors that intersect with public services, such as healthcare and education. These partnerships not only drive innovation but also contribute to the overall strengthening of the startup ecosystem in Greece.

To harness these opportunities, there's a need for more focused efforts on creating synergies among the stakeholders in the startup ecosystem. Encouraging multidisciplinary collaboration can spur innovation, especially in the emerging sectors. Also, enhancing relationships with international partners can further open doors to global markets.

These opportunities, if leveraged well, can significantly impact the growth and competitiveness of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Greece. They offer the possibility of turning weaknesses into strengths and threats into opportunities, especially when coupled with strategic planning and execution.

Threats

Economic Volatility: The Greek economy has faced significant turbulence over the years, with substantial focus on the financial crisis that started in 2008. This crisis exposed Greece's weak financial foundations, including growing macroeconomic imbalances, large public debt, and weak institutions, and led to three Economic Adjustment Programmes in 2010, 2012, and 2015.

Figure 9: The chronology of the Greek crisis [28]

The European Commission's audit [28] highlighted several weaknesses in these programs. Despite bringing some reforms and fiscal savings, the programs fell short in crucial areas like structural reforms in taxation and public administration. The program's primary objectives—return to growth, fiscal sustainability, and financial stability—were achieved only to a limited extent. For instance, Greece's GDP shrunk by over a quarter during the programs, and its debt to GDP ratio increased, affecting investor confidence and economic stability.

Such a backdrop of economic volatility and the limitations of financial adjustment programs contribute to an environment of caution among investors, potentially leading to a reduction in funding opportunities for young companies.

Competition from Maturing Global Ecosystems: The rise of startup ecosystems in other parts of Europe and the world poses a competitive threat to Greece. Countries with more mature ecosystems offer more resources, better support structures, and more lucrative markets, attracting both talent and investment away from Greece. To remain competitive, Greek startups can focus on niche sectors where the country has inherent strengths or emerging opportunities, such as eHealth

or AgriTech. Collaborating with international partners can also help in scaling and gaining global traction.

Potential Adverse Changes in Government or EU Policies: Changes in government policies or EU regulations can adversely affect the startup ecosystem. For instance, increased corporate taxes or more stringent labour laws can discourage entrepreneurship and limit startups' ability to scale effectively. Active engagement with policymakers can help in shaping a more favourable business environment. The startup community, perhaps through industry associations, should aim to have a seat at the table when policies affecting them are being discussed.

Disruptive Technologies: While technological advancements offer opportunities, they can also pose threats, especially for startups that are not agile enough to adapt. New technologies can quickly render existing solutions obsolete. Investing in continuous learning and upskilling can help startups stay ahead of the technological curve. An innovation-focused culture can also assist in quick adaptation to new technologies.

Each of these threats requires strategic attention to build resilience within Greece's entrepreneurial ecosystem. Proactive planning, coupled with effective mitigation strategies, can go a long way in converting these external threats into challenges that can be overcome. This will contribute to the ecosystem's long-term stability and growth.

Bulgaria

SWOT Analysis

This section offers a detailed SWOT analysis of the Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem, breaking down its Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. We aim to highlight the main factors driving its growth and challenges. Key points are summarized in a SWOT Matrix, shown in Figure 1. This analysis helps pinpoint key areas for improvement and potential future trends in the ecosystem.

The SWOT analysis provided below is tailored towards the Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem. However, some of the points touch upon broader macroeconomic and societal issues because they directly or indirectly impact the entrepreneurial landscape. For instance, demographic trends and the size of the national market are macroeconomic factors, but they have implications for the entrepreneurial ecosystem in terms of available talent, market size, and growth opportunities.

It's essential to consider these broader factors when analyzing the entrepreneurial ecosystem because they provide context and highlight the external challenges and opportunities that entrepreneurs in Bulgaria might face.

Figure 10: SWOT Matrix showcasing the key factors shaping Bulgaria's entrepreneurial landscape

Strengths

Positive macroeconomic development trends and low taxes: Bulgaria has consistently showcased positive macroeconomic indicators, making it an attractive destination for businesses. The country's GDP growth, low unemployment rate, and stable inflation have contributed to a conducive business environment. Furthermore, Bulgaria boasts one of the lowest corporate tax rates in the European Union at 10%, which is particularly appealing to both domestic and foreign investors. This competitive tax regime has played a significant role in attracting investments and fostering entrepreneurial activities.

Advanced telecommunication services, particularly in the ICT sector: Bulgaria's investment in its ICT infrastructure over the years has been commendable. The nation's robust telecommunication network supports high-speed internet connectivity, making it ideal for tech startups and digital businesses. This infrastructure has been pivotal in attracting IT outsourcing and establishing Bulgaria

as a preferred destination for tech companies. The country's digital readiness ensures that businesses can operate seamlessly and cater to global clients.

Diverse and skilled talent pool, especially in the tech sector: Bulgaria's education system, particularly in STEM fields, produces a steady stream of skilled professionals. A significant portion of the population holds secondary and tertiary educational qualifications, ensuring a steady supply of skilled professionals. The country has a rich talent pool of software developers, engineers, and tech specialists, making it a hub for tech startups and IT outsourcing.

Existence of high-growth enterprises and tradition in basic and applied research: Bulgaria has a longstanding tradition in research and development. Over the years, this has translated into the emergence of high-growth enterprises, especially in the tech and innovation sectors. The country's research institutions and universities have been at the forefront of various scientific advancements. This culture of research and innovation provides a solid foundation for startups and businesses looking to break new ground.

Leading qualified researchers in various scientific fields: Bulgaria is home to some of the leading researchers in multiple scientific domains. These experts are not just limited to academia but also collaborate with businesses, providing them with cutting-edge solutions and innovations. Their expertise spans across fields like IT, biotechnology, engineering, and more. This pool of qualified researchers ensures that businesses in Bulgaria have access to the latest research and can stay at the forefront of innovation.

Supportive governmental policies and initiatives for startups: The Bulgarian government acknowledges the pivotal role of startups and entrepreneurship in driving economic progress. To this end, a suite of supportive measures has been introduced, ranging from financial incentives to streamlined regulations. The 2022 inception of the Ministry of Innovation and Growth (MIR) marks a deliberate effort to centralize and enhance initiatives centered on innovation and national economic advancement. Key measures include the creation of the National Innovation Fund, designed to nurture startups during their formative stages. The "Innovation and Competitiveness" Operational Program offers tools like the Acceleration and Seed Fund, as well as the Venture Capital Fund, all aimed at bolstering entrepreneurial ventures and ensuring SMEs have adequate financial resources. The Business Booster Online Platform [25] stands as a valuable guide for emerging entrepreneurs, providing insights into best business practices. Furthermore, recent policy changes now allow public universities to set up companies, promoting the translation of research into market-ready solutions.

Presence of specialized clusters, technology parks, and innovation hubs, incubators, and co-working space : Bulgaria offers a range of amenities specifically designed to nurture budding entrepreneurs. Clusters like the Automotive Cluster Bulgaria [20], ICT Cluster [19], AI Cluster [22] and the Bulgarian Furniture Cluster [21] are examples of industry-specific groupings that promote collaboration, innovation, and competitiveness within their respective sectors. From state-of-the-art incubators and accelerators that provide mentorship and funding to networking events that foster collaboration, the infrastructure is in place to support startups at every stage of their journey. Sofia Tech Park [18] stands as a prime example of state-supported innovation, offering a blend of incubation, research facilities, and events to foster growth. Incubators and accelerators such as Eleven [10] and LAUNCHub [11] provide startups with essential mentorship and resources.

Growing reputation as a tech and innovation hub in Southeast Europe: Bulgaria's ascent as a prominent tech and innovation hub in Southeast Europe is evident from its strategic advancements in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector. The nation boasts advanced telecommunication services, which have become the foundation for a burgeoning tech industry, attracting both local and international stakeholders. This growth is further underscored by the significant expansion of the ICT sector, including its exports, and the high wages associated with it. The presence of ICT clusters across Bulgaria and the active participation of local investment funds tailored for ICT ventures showcase the country's dedication to nurturing its tech ecosystem. Moreover, leading multinational companies have recognized Bulgaria's potential, establishing their research centres within its borders. These centres not only bring expertise but also significantly contribute to the local economy and job market.

Additionally, Bulgaria's engagement with major international tech giants facilitates knowledge exchange and collaboration, while the broad implementation of innovations and the focus on fostering an entrepreneurial spirit among the youth promise a bright future for the tech ecosystem. The nation's forward-thinking approach, as seen in the potential for widespread ICT integration in enterprises, solidifies its position as a tech-forward leader in the region.

Weaknesses

Negative demographic trends, including population and labor force aging: Bulgaria's population is estimated to shrink by 23% by 2050, making it one of the fastest-shrinking nations globally [26]. This demographic challenge, coupled with an aging population where nearly 20% are over 65 [26], poses a threat to the availability of skilled labor. A declining workforce can impact the dynamism of the entrepreneurial ecosystem and limit the pool of young entrepreneurs and innovators.

A small national market, limiting demand growth opportunities: With a population of just over 7 million, Bulgaria's domestic market is relatively small. This size can restrict the scalability opportunities for businesses, especially those heavily reliant on local demand. For startups, this means potentially hitting a growth ceiling early unless they expand internationally.

Specialization in low and medium technology sectors: While Bulgaria has a burgeoning IT sector, contributing around 4% to the national GDP, its industrial landscape is notably marked by a concentration in medium and low technological industries, which encompass 9.3% of the total enterprises [27]. In contrast, high-tech activities contribute a smaller fraction to the economy. The ICT sector, while growing, is predominantly influenced by the wholesale trade of computer and communication equipment, with manufacturing-related enterprises in this sector making up just 5.6% [27]. Labor productivity in low-tech activities stands at 75.5% of the industry and service sector average [27]. Even though there's an emerging significance of the high-tech domain, especially with startups in ICT, mechatronics, and microelectronics, Bulgaria's historical manufacturing strengths in medium and low-tech sectors from the 1980s remain dominant in its economic structure.

Shortage of skilled labour force and low labour productivity: Despite 33.6% of Bulgarians aged 25-34 having completed tertiary education in 2021 [28], there's a gap between available skills and market requirements. This mismatch has led to labour shortages in specific sectors, such as IT, where there are an estimated 5,000 vacant positions annually.

High share of the grey sector and limited innovation dynamics: Large part of Bulgaria's GDP is estimated to be part of the grey economy. Such a significant portion can stifle the growth of the legitimate entrepreneurial ecosystem. Limited innovation activities, with Bulgaria spending just 0.78% of its GDP on R&D in 2019 [27], further hinder the nation's entrepreneurial potential.

Fragmented research system and low R&D expenditure: Despite having research institutions, Bulgaria's landscape is fragmented, with limited collaboration between academia and industry. The

country's R&D expenditure, at less than 1% of GDP [27], is one of the lowest in the EU, indicating a need for increased investment in innovation.

Limited alignment between education and market needs: While Bulgaria has a literacy rate of over 98% [29], the curricula of educational institutions sometimes don't align with evolving market demands. This misalignment can lead to skill gaps, especially in emerging sectors like fintech, AI, and biotech.

Challenges in the regulatory environment specific to startups: While Bulgaria has made strides in improving its business environment, startups often face bureaucratic hurdles. Complex registration processes, lack of clarity in regulations, and challenges in accessing public funding can impede their growth and operations in the Bulgarian market.

These weaknesses, if not addressed, could slow down the development and competitiveness of the Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem. Therefore, targeted interventions in these areas are crucial for fortifying the ecosystem's growth and stability.

Opportunities

Potential to tap into underrepresented sectors like microelectronics, mechatronics, biotech, robotics, deep tech, etc. The nation's robust IT foundation positions it well to delve into cloud computing, offering scalable solutions tailored for diverse industries. The emphasis on biotechnological advancements globally also opens doors for Bulgaria in genetic engineering and personalized medicine. As technology becomes increasingly integrated into our lives, there's a growing need for advancements in human-computer interaction, ensuring products are user-centric. Robotics, another burgeoning field, offers Bulgaria an opportunity to become a regional leader, especially given its tech talent. Furthermore, the nation's research institutions can pioneer in materials science, potentially revolutionizing industries from construction to electronics. With the digital realm expanding, cybersecurity emerges as a crucial sector, and Bulgaria's IT prowess can cater to global demands. Additionally, the realms of data science, AI, nanotechnology, and aerospace engineering present opportunities for Bulgaria to establish itself as an innovation hub in Southeast Europe.

Expansion of digital infrastructure and e-governance: Digital infrastructure is the backbone of modern economies. While Bulgaria boasts impressive broadband speeds in urban areas, there's potential for expansion in rural regions, ensuring nationwide connectivity. This not only facilitates

business operations but also ensures that the entire population can benefit from digital advancements. On the e-governance front, Bulgaria has made strides with initiatives like electronic ID cards and online administrative services. However, there's room for further integration, such as comprehensive e-health systems, digitalized land registries, and more. Such advancements can significantly reduce bureaucratic inefficiencies and improve public service delivery.

Potential for increased collaboration between academia and businesses for innovation: Bulgaria's academic institutions, particularly its universities, are reservoirs of research and innovation. However, there's often a gap between academic research and its commercial application. By establishing tech transfer offices, promoting university-industry collaboration, and incentivizing research with commercial potential, Bulgaria can bridge this gap. Such initiatives can lead to spin-off companies, patent registrations, and the commercialization of research, enhancing the country's innovation output.

Expanding Access to EU and Non-EU Markets: Bulgaria can leverage its position and networks to access both EU and non-EU markets, providing a broader platform for startups and businesses to scale and reach new customers. This expansion can be facilitated by utilizing existing trade agreements and exploring new partnerships that align with the nation's economic and innovation objectives.

Introduction of Waste-Free Technologies: The adoption and development of waste-free technologies that are environmentally friendly can position Bulgaria as a leader in sustainable business practices. This not only aligns with global sustainability trends but also opens avenues for innovation in green technologies, which is a growing sector globally.

Leveraging EU funds and programs to support startups: The European Union offers a plethora of funds and programs aimed at promoting innovation, research, and entrepreneurship. Bulgaria, by effectively tapping into these resources, can supercharge its entrepreneurial ecosystem. This involves not just securing funds but also ensuring that they are channeled effectively. Workshops, information campaigns, and streamlined application processes can ensure that Bulgarian startups and enterprises are well-equipped to access and utilize these funds.

Strengthening of the regulatory framework to further support startups and entrepreneurial activities: The regulatory environment plays a pivotal role in shaping the entrepreneurial landscape. While Bulgaria has made commendable efforts in this direction, continuous evaluation and adaptation are crucial. This involves engaging with stakeholders, including startups, investors, and

experts, to understand the challenges they face and adapt regulations accordingly. For instance, simplifying the company registration process, offering tax breaks for R&D activities, or introducing sandbox environments for testing innovative solutions can go a long way in promoting entrepreneurship.

To optimize its entrepreneurial ecosystem, Bulgaria should focus on several key strategies. Investing in high-potential sectors like biotech, robotics, and advanced technologies is essential. This can be amplified by seeking international partnerships and collaborations. Enhancing digital infrastructure, particularly in underserved regions, and fast-tracking e-governance will streamline public services. Strengthening ties between universities and businesses can ensure research translates into market-ready solutions. Tapping into EU funds, with a streamlined application process, can provide startups with the necessary financial boost. Regulatory adjustments, specifically catering to startups, can create a more innovation-friendly environment. Adjusting the educational curriculum to include entrepreneurial skills and offering specialized training can equip the next generation with the tools they need. Promoting Bulgaria through targeted marketing can attract both local and foreign talent and investors. Lastly, introducing financial incentives, such as R&D tax credits, can spur innovation and attract more businesses to the Bulgarian ecosystem.

Threats

Negative demographic trends leading to potential labour shortages: Bulgaria's population has been on a steady decline, with projections indicating a drop from 7 million in 2020 to 5.4 million by 2050 [30]. This demographic shift, characterized by an aging populace and a decline in birth rates, poses challenges for the labour market. A contracting working-age population could lead to shortages in skilled labour, especially in sectors requiring specialized skills. This might result in increased wage demands, further straining businesses. This demographic shift is not just a statistical concern; it has tangible implications for the country's labour market. As the number of retirees grows, the working-age population contracts, leading to a potential shortage of skilled labour. Industries that rely heavily on specialized skills, such as tech startups or advanced manufacturing, might find it increasingly challenging to recruit the right talent. This could result in companies resorting to hiring from abroad or even relocating their operations to countries with a more favorable demographic profile. Furthermore, a reduced workforce might lead to increased wage demands, further straining businesses.

Dependence on a few sectors, risking economic stability: While Bulgaria boasts a diverse economic landscape, it leans heavily on certain sectors like tourism, agriculture, and textiles. For example, Bulgaria's GDP composition reveals a heavy reliance on sectors like tourism, which contributes around 12% to the GDP [31]. Such dependence makes the nation's economic health susceptible to global fluctuations in these sectors. For instance, a global downturn in tourism due to unforeseen events can significantly impact Bulgaria's revenue streams. To safeguard against such vulnerabilities, there's a pressing need for Bulgaria to diversify its economic activities, encouraging growth in emerging sectors and reducing reliance on traditionally dominant ones.

Potential brain drain due to emigration of skilled professionals: The allure of better opportunities, higher salaries, and improved living standards in Western European countries or North America has led many of Bulgaria's skilled professionals to emigrate. Bulgaria has witnessed a significant emigration rate, with over 2 million Bulgarians living abroad as of 2020 [32]. This exodus is not just a loss of workforce but a depletion of the nation's intellectual capital. When skilled professionals, be it doctors, engineers, or academics, choose to pursue careers abroad, Bulgaria loses out on their potential contributions to its socio-economic development. This trend can stifle innovation, hinder research endeavours, and slow down the nation's progress in various fields.

Challenges in the regulatory environment specific to startups: While Bulgaria ranks 61st in the Ease of Doing Business Index [33], startups often face regulatory challenges. Complex procedures for business registration, ambiguous tax structures, and difficulties in accessing institutional funding can deter budding entrepreneurs. These challenges can also make Bulgaria less attractive to foreign investors, who might opt for countries with a more streamlined regulatory framework. Addressing these issues requires not just policy changes but also efforts to raise awareness about these policies among the entrepreneurial community.

Limited alignment between education and market needs, leading to skill gaps: The dynamic nature of today's industries necessitates an equally dynamic educational framework. However, despite having a literacy rate of over 98% [29], there's a perceived gap between the skills imparted by Bulgarian educational institutions and market demands. This gap can result in graduates who, despite being academically proficient, lack the practical skills needed in the workplace. To bridge this gap, there's a need for closer collaboration between academia and industry, curriculum overhauls to incorporate contemporary skills, and an emphasis on practical exposure.

High share of the grey sector: The informal or grey sector in Bulgaria, while providing livelihoods to many, poses challenges to the nation's economic framework. It accounts for nearly 30% of the country's GDP [34]. Operating outside the purview of formal regulations, this sector often evades taxation, leading to significant revenue losses for the government. Additionally, businesses in the grey sector are deprived of the benefits of formal financial systems, such as loans or insurance, which can limit their growth prospects. Tackling this issue requires a multi-pronged approach, including awareness campaigns, incentives for formalization, and stricter regulatory measures.

Each of these threats necessitates careful planning to fortify Bulgaria's entrepreneurial landscape. By adopting forward-thinking measures and efficient countermeasures, these potential risks can be transformed into surmountable obstacles. Such efforts will bolster the ecosystem's enduring progress and expansion.

Turkiye

SWOT Analysis

This section provides a detailed SWOT analysis of the Turkish entrepreneurial ecosystem, evaluating its Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. This comprehensive analysis aims to capture the range of factors that contribute to the ecosystem's development, growth, and competitiveness. The insights have been summarized for quick reference in a SWOT Matrix, depicted in Figure 10. The analysis serves to identify crucial areas for development, existing limitations, and potential risks and opportunities that could influence the ecosystem's future.

Figure 11- SWOT Matrix showcasing the key factors shaping Turkiye's entrepreneurial landscape

Strengths

Large size of internal market: The size of the internal market in Turkiye serves as an important advantage for startups. Turkiye's population stands at approximately 85 million, and half of the population is under 33.5 years old (Invest in Turkiye, 2023). It creates a dynamic population and labour force which are more prone to adopt new technologies and innovations. The size of the domestic market provides startups with a large customer base for rapid growth and scalability. Although Turkiye's GDP is lower than the European Union average, the size and the composition of the country's population reveals a potential to overcome this advantage. According to the European

Comparison Program for 2022, GDP per capita index based on purchasing power parity in Türkiye was 69 while the average for EU countries was 100, and it was 31 percent below the EU average¹⁹.

Although lower GDP per capita has a negative effect on startups' scalability especially in high-tech industries and markets, the size of the domestic market has a balancing positive impact. Moreover, the size of the domestic market also attracts international investors, especially international venture capital. However, unicorns need global expansion beyond the borders of the country. Despite the challenges of international expansion most of the Turkish startups are looking for opportunities at the global scale.

Size of the young, educated population: One of the most significant assets of the Turkish entrepreneurial ecosystem is its young population with high education. According to OECD Report,²⁰ 41.2% of the young adult population (25-34 years old) in Türkiye has a tertiary education. Young and well-educated population of Türkiye is approximately 31 million (Invest in Türkiye, 2022). Every year, around 900 thousand young people graduate from universities. The size of the young and educated population makes Türkiye more competitive at the global scale in terms of human capital which is crucial for any startup ecosystem. Skilled professionals contribute to innovation and technological advancements, key drivers for a startup's success.

Supportive Infrastructure: Since the beginning of the 1990s, Türkiye has invested in development of technology clusters, technology parks, TTOs, incubation programs or R&D centres. By January 2021, there are 87 techno parks across Türkiye and more than 6000 companies with approximately 55,000 R&D personnel are in these techno parks. ICT and software development has the highest sectoral share in techno parks with 45% (TTGV, 2020). Approximately 1300 R&D centres have been established by private companies. Among those centres, 210 belong to a foreign firm or a firm with foreign shareholders. The number of incubation and acceleration programs and co-working spaces has been increasing for the last decade. These spaces and programs are crucial to create a supportive infrastructure to nurture new ventures by enabling collaboration, knowledge and information exchange and financial and non-financial support.

Government Initiatives: The Turkish government has shown commitment to support entrepreneurship and various stakeholders of the entrepreneurship ecosystem. TUBITAK's "1513 Technology Transfer Offices Grant Programme", "1601 Capacity Building for Innovation and

¹⁹ [https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Purchasing-Power-Parity-\(Temp\)-2022-49757&dil=2](https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Purchasing-Power-Parity-(Temp)-2022-49757&dil=2)

²⁰ OECD, "Population with tertiary education (indicator)," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1787/0b8f90e9-en>. [Accessed 30 08 2023].

Entrepreneurship Grant Programme” (Investment Office 2020; TUBITAK 2019) are the examples of support schemes and grants for the development of TTOs and incubation/acceleration programs in Turkiye. 1512 Capital Support Program (BIGG) is designed to support individual entrepreneurs to transform their technology and innovation-oriented business ideas into startups. 1514 Venture Capital Support Program developed to enable venture capital funds to invest in R&D intensive early-stage companies. These government initiatives create an environment for nurturing startups.

Strategic location and exposure to international markets: Due to the geographic location, Turkiye has access to both European Union markets and the countries in the MENA region. The Customs Union with the EU allows access to the European market. Turkiye has Free Trade Agreements with 28 countries (Invest in Turkiye, 2023). International exchange programs allow Turkish University students to have a global perspective. international exposure and a global perspective. Furthermore, international accelerator programs, Silicon Valley tours and similar international programs for startups encourage Turkish startups to realise their internationalisation dreams.

Weaknesses

Lower business sophistication: One of the most significant barriers for startups in Turkiye is that the internal market demand is not very sophisticated. In other words, the demand for innovative products is lower; this makes growth and scalability of innovative startups difficult. The Global Competitiveness Index also indicates that Turkiye is not very competitive in terms of business sophistication²¹. The ratio of high-technology products in manufacturing industries exports was 2.8% in January-September 2022 period (TUIK, 2022). Gross domestic spending on R&D in 2021 equals to 1.13% of the GDP²².

Bureaucratic hurdles and complexity of legislation: Legislation and regulations to apply for various support schemes, export, taxing, tax redemptions are very complicated, difficult to understand and interpret for inexperienced entrepreneurs. Furthermore, the frequent amendments in the regulations increase bureaucratic complexity for new ventures to operate. There are various support schemes under different programs, application to these programs demand entrepreneurs to know

²¹ World Economic Forum, The Global Competitiveness Index, Turkey (2017-2018) Available online at https://www3.weforum.org/docs/GCR2017-2018/03CountryProfiles/Standalone2-pagerprofiles/WEF_GCI_2017_2018_Profile_Turkey.pdf

²² OECD(2022). Gross domestic spending on R&D. Available online at <https://data.oecd.org/rd/gross-domestic-spending-on-r-d.htm>

the details of each support scheme. Lack of flexibility in the application of these support programs and regulations has a negative impact on the dynamism of the entrepreneurship ecosystem.

Lower cooperation and collaboration among stakeholders: Although there are initiatives and efforts to improve the collaboration among various stakeholders of the ecosystem, this has not been achieved yet. The interest of large and medium size incumbents to entrepreneurship is very limited. Most of these companies are not innovative and operate in traditional sectors. Such a landscape downwards the collaboration between startups and corporations and hence, their capability to scale. University-industry relations are limited. Most universities do not have strong relationships with the actors in their local ecosystem.

Limited Venture Funding: There are various funding mechanisms, such as venture capital, angel investors, and public funding programs in Turkiye. New support schemes and legislation have been introduced by public organisations to stimulate venture funding. However, securing early-stage funding remains a significant challenge for startups. The local venture capital ecosystem is relatively nascent, especially when compared to more developed startup landscapes. Furthermore, existing private investment initiatives often prioritise less risky ventures, and public initiatives are also difficult to access due to competition. As a result, startups in their initial stages find themselves with limited options for seed and pre-seed funding, constraining their ability to turn innovative ideas into scalable businesses. This is one of the most important limitations that must be addressed in the Turkish entrepreneurship ecosystem to support the emergence of new startups and increase survival rates.

Limited human capital specialised in entrepreneurship: Although public support schemes have aimed to achieve capacity development and formation of human capital specialised in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial processes, the number of academics, the number of mentors and professionals in incubation and acceleration programs to provide support to entrepreneurs is still limited in size. In high schools and tertiary education, the human capital to teach entrepreneurship in full capacity is scarce. VCs have difficulties attracting qualified new graduates. This shortfall creates a hurdle for the entrepreneurship ecosystem to create and support new ventures.

To overcome these weaknesses, there is a need for policies and support to increase the innovation capacity of firms and their technological awareness, streamlined regulatory processes making startups access to support, to encourage collaborations between ecosystem stakeholders. Increasing

the funding opportunities for early-stage startups could also support the emergence of new ventures and their survival rates. Development of human capital specialised in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial education and processes is also necessary to meet the needs of startups and other ecosystem stakeholders while the ecosystem is enlarging and the number of young people who are interested in entrepreneurship is increasing.

These weaknesses should be addressed to ensure the development and competitiveness of the Turkish entrepreneurial ecosystem. Therefore, targeted interventions in these areas are crucial for fortifying the ecosystem's growth and stability.

Opportunities

Widening support with new legislations: An amendment to the Law on Technology Development Zones (Law No: 7263) on 03.02.2021²³ requires the companies that exceed a certain scale in Technoparks or have benefited from R&D and design grants to invest in VCIF. This brought a new wave of intrapreneurs from large corporations, turning into entrepreneurs with the support of their employers. The holding companies increasingly arrange entrepreneurship competitions within their employees and provide incubation support as well as VC investment through their investment funds. This new arrangement increasingly gives rise to spin-off ventures from large corporations founded by their talented employees with valuable business experience and knowledge.

New hubs in emerging sectors: While the Turkish economy historically relied on the manufacturing sectors, in which capital requirement is high and rapid growth is difficult, the last decade gave rise to a large group of entrepreneurs in emerging software business fields, especially in fintech and the gaming industry. The network and knowledge spillover effects of those new hubs is expected to foster the birth and growth of ventures in those fields, where rapid scaling and global access is easier. Moreover, the recent birth of unicorns from Turkiye in the emerging fields has been a source of motivation and self-efficacy for many Turkish entrepreneurs.

Applying new technologies to manufacturing: With a high share of manufacturing in the economy, Turkiye promises its prospective entrepreneurs opportunities in advanced manufacturing applications. Several Turkish startups, especially the ones located in the techno parks, work on emerging opportunities in product simulation and modeling, robotic process automation, advanced materials design, flexible production solutions, big data analytics and artificial intelligence, enhanced

²³ <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2021/02/20210203-11.htm>

cybersecurity, and predictive maintenance. Thanks to the size and variety of the manufacturing sectors in the country, those entrepreneurs have an immediate large potential customer base with which they can also collaborate to develop and test their products.

Growing Health and Education markets: Türkiye fastly rises as a regional hub for health and education services. While the Europeans prefer the country in health services for their much cheaper prices with good quality, the Middle East and African citizens increasingly prefer Turkish education institutions for their quality education at lower prices compared to the West. This situation not only increases growth potential for local companies in those sectors, but also creates new segments to offer additional services as well as new international networks for the Turkish citizens.

Türkiye as a rising ICT nation: Türkiye has one of the fastest growing ICT sectors in the globe. The average growth of the ICT sector in 5 has years has been 23%, to reach a market size of Usd 30 billion by 2021²⁴. From 2023 to 2028, the market is expected to grow with a compound annual growth rate of 9.3%²⁵. There are more than 2000 active ICT companies in the country and more than 185.000 employees in the ICT sector, 58% of which are younger than 35 years old. In 2022, 94.1% of households had access to the internet from home in 2022, and 85% of individuals between 16-74 age group regularly uses the internet²⁶. Turkish businesses of all sizes are integrating cutting-edge ICT tools in their operations. Artificial Intelligence is increasingly used in the fintech industry to carry out tasks such as fraud detection, lending decision-making, credit risk assessment, customer service, wealth management, insurance, etc. In addition, to meet the 5G requirements throughout the nation, the Turkish government has formed the New Generation Mobile Communication Technology forum, which comprises universities, operators, NGOs, and manufacturers.

Increased support by state organisations and NGOs: In recent years, Turkish state organizations have started to actively support the entrepreneurship ecosystem through platforms such as Turcorn, Turquality, Fintech Hub, International Incubation Center. Similarly, established foundations and associations operating in the field or adjacent areas have started support programs for the specific needs of entrepreneurs. Technology Development Foundation of Türkiye (TTGV)'s HİT program specifically focuses on speeding up the first customer/first sales processes, providing an accurate

²⁴ <https://www.invest.gov.tr/en/sectors/pages/ict.aspx>

²⁵ <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/turkey-ict-market>

²⁶ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=45587&dil=2>

assessment of commercialization potential, and facilitating access to early-stage investment opportunities. Idea to Business Center, a foundation established by the Istanbul Chamber of Commerce specifically focuses on commercialising innovative business ideas. It offers free-of-charge services such as training and seminars, mentor support, investor matching, demo day events, 24/7 office facilities, and one-on-one consultancy.

To harness these opportunities, there's a need for more focused efforts on creating synergies among the stakeholders in the startup ecosystem. These opportunities, if leveraged well, can significantly impact the growth and competitiveness of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Türkiye. They offer the possibility of turning weaknesses into strengths and threats into opportunities, especially when coupled with strategic planning and execution.

Threats

Investment squeeze: One risk for the ecosystem is the exhaustion of global interest in the Turkish ecosystem. Turkish startups reached unicorn status with the international exits, global VC funds investing in Turkish startups play a vital role in the ecosystem in this process. This interest was attracted through the global success of Turkish mobile gaming, e-grocery, and e-commerce startups (DEIK, 2022). However, due to economic risks associated with economic and financial volatility, the interest of global VCs can diminish. Another risk is related to the preference of VCs to invest in the Turkish ecosystem. Most of the VC investments are seed and early-stage investments. In Europe, late-stage capital accounted for 73.6% however this ratio is less than 40% in Türkiye (DEIK, 2022). Furthermore, after the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and the World Bank limited their long-term investment loans for the country, there has hardly been any chances left for long-term borrowing. The local banks can facilitate relatively small amounts of syndicated loans that are short-term, such as 367 days, and have high spreads due to the high CDS score of Türkiye. This constitutes a big challenge especially for the startups in capital-intensive businesses. After they go through rounds of VC and equity investments, those companies still need long-term finance to be able to scale as fast as their competitors in countries such as India and China, where the governments actively support the ventures with massive amounts of investment finance. All these problems may lead to an investment squeeze to early and late-stage startups and may slow down the growth of the ecosystem.

Brain drain: Recent years saw a big brain drain of qualified Turkish citizens to countries including mostly Germany, USA, Canada and the UK. Economic and social challenges that the qualified

population of Türkiye have faced led to a large group of talented and highly educated individuals in key sectors to move abroad. Moreover, Turkish students studying abroad increasingly prefer to stay in the Western countries to seek opportunities. This is a threat that may erode the social capital and slow down the growth pace of high value-added entrepreneurial activity.

Outflow of high-potential startups from the country: Many high-potential startups born in Türkiye move their headquarters to the US or the EU countries, for reasons such as easier access to capital, access to markets, more supportive legislation, and regulations for entrepreneurs or just because they want to live there. Despite being educated in Türkiye and benefiting from the local entrepreneurship ecosystem when starting their business, these startups do not feed the local economy nor the ecosystem once they grow.

Data localization measures: The Turkish government issued a new legislation to ban the transfer of data of Turkish citizens to servers located abroad. Accordingly, the companies are required to store data in local servers and use local sim cards for the IoT services. This situation poses a threat to the spread of newly emerging global ICT services and to the growth of the sector as well as the knowledge accumulation.

Economic Volatility: Aftermath of the pandemic era has been a big challenge for Türkiye. At present, the global outlook on Türkiye's investment climate is negative. Report of the US State Department in 2020 indicates Türkiye's economic policymaking as opaque and unforeseeable and emphasises that factors such as high inflation, exchange rate volatility and data localization measures impact risk perception negatively²⁷. Combined with the pandemic induced recession, and decrease of foreign direct investment in developing countries, the country risk becomes more pressing (DEIK, 2022). By June 2023, Türkiye changed the economic policies to ensure economic stability, to prevent currency fluctuations and decrease inflation rate.

Earthquake's effects on economy: Türkiye was hit by two devastating earthquakes in February 2022, and eleven of its cities were severely harmed. While the earthquakes did not hit the biggest industry zones of the country, the infrastructure investments and aid for the victims of the earthquake is expected to cause a big burden on the state economy. The share of the construction industry in the economy, which had started to decrease in recent years, is expected to rise because of the necessary houses, building, roads, and infrastructure works for the earthquake-hit zones. The additional taxes aimed at creating funds for the state to remedy earthquake's effects have put some

²⁷ '2020 Investment Climate Statements: Türkiye', United States Department of State (blog), accessed 19 April 2022, <https://www.state.gov/reports/2020-investment-climate-statements/Türkiye/>

burden on the enterprises and individuals. Combined with economic volatility, this may lead to a decrease in R&D and innovation investments.

Each of these threats requires attention to strengthen the Turkish entrepreneurship ecosystem. A careful and comprehensive approach to these threats is crucial for effective planning that can decrease the potential harmful effects of these threats. Any strategic planning designed to overcome or mitigate these threats will contribute to the ecosystem's long-term stability and growth.

France

SWOT Analysis

Fig 12. SWOT Matrix showcasing the key factors shaping Bulgaria's entrepreneurial landscape

This section provides a comprehensive SWOT analysis of the French entrepreneurial ecosystem, evaluating its Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. The analysis aims to assess internal factors that might affect the entrepreneurial ecosystem (strengths and weaknesses) and external factors (opportunities and threats). The analysis provides a basis for developing strategies to achieve development objectives, improve efficiency and international competition.

Strengths

Government Support: Strong government backing through initiatives like Bpifrance and La French Tech. The French government also offers robust support for startups through various programs and incentives. Bpifrance, for example, provides **funding**, guarantees, and loans to entrepreneurs,

reducing financial barriers to entry. The government has implemented regulatory reforms to simplify business processes and promote entrepreneurship. These reforms aim to reduce administrative burdens and encourage startups to flourish.

Research and Innovation: France is home to renowned world class research institutions and universities, such as the Sorbonne and CNRS (National Center for Scientific Research), fostering a culture of innovation and excellence. Collaboration between academia, HEIs and RCs and industry facilitates the transfer of cutting-edge research into commercial applications, supporting startups with access to advanced technologies.

Tech Hubs and supportive spaces: Tech hubs and supportive spaces are integral strengths of the French entrepreneurial ecosystem. They create physical and virtual environments where startups can thrive, collaborate, and access essential resources. These spaces serve as catalysts for innovation, networking, and community building, making them critical assets in the development of successful startups and the growth of the entrepreneurial ecosystem as a whole.

Station F in Paris is one of the world's largest startup campuses, housing over a thousand startups, investors, and support organizations under one roof. This massive hub provides an ecosystem where entrepreneurs can work, collaborate, and learn from one another. It fosters cross-pollination of ideas and innovation across diverse industries. And beyond Paris, several other French cities have developed their own tech hubs, such as Lyon, Marseille, and Toulouse. These regional hubs play a crucial role in decentralizing the startup ecosystem and supporting entrepreneurship across the country, providing local tech opportunities for talented youth.

Access to EU and global markets: France's central location in Europe provides startups with easy access to a vast and diverse European and the global market, serving as a gateway to EU member states and beyond for internationalization

Diverse industries: France boasts a diverse economy with strongholds in various industries, including aerospace, automotive, fashion, and agritech. This diversity offers startups opportunities to collaborate with established companies, access specialized resources, and tap into well-defined markets. The presence of industry-specific clusters and associations encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing within sectors, promoting innovation and growth.

Welcoming international start-ups: France has made significant strides in attracting international entrepreneurs and talent. The French Tech Visa program, which simplifies visa procedures for non-European startup founders, presents an opportunity to bring in fresh ideas and international

networks. Collaborations with entrepreneurs from diverse backgrounds can lead to innovative solutions and broader market access.

Quality of life: France offers an excellent quality of life, with world-class healthcare, education, cultural experiences, and a strong work-life balance. This quality of life attracts both domestic and international talent, enhancing the ecosystem's appeal to entrepreneurs.

Talent pool: France boasts a highly educated and skilled workforce. The country is home to world-renowned universities and research institutions, producing a steady stream of graduates with expertise in various fields, including technology, science, engineering, business, and the arts. This talent pool provides startups with access to a diverse range of skills and expertise, and is a significant strength that underpins the success of its entrepreneurial ecosystem. It provides startups with access to a diverse, educated, and innovative workforce that can drive innovation, fuel growth, and contribute to the overall competitiveness of the ecosystem on the global stage.

Weaknesses

Bureaucracy: France's administrative processes and complex labor laws can be barriers for startups, particularly for smaller businesses and foreign entrepreneurs. Despite efforts to streamline regulations, navigating bureaucracy can still be challenging for startups, potentially slowing down business operations.

Language barrier: While English is widely spoken in the business world, in France fewer businessmen speak English, which can be a hurdle for non-French-speaking entrepreneurs. Although the French language is a cultural pride, the fact that not many people outside of big cities speak English poses problems for incoming international start-up founders.

Funding Gap: While funding options have improved, some startups may still find it challenging to secure significant venture capital compared to ecosystems like Silicon Valley. The French institutional support aims at start-ups at the very beginning stage (tree-seed and seed), and practically ignores the needs of mature start-ups that need to raise substantial funds to scale.

Cultural resistance to risk: There is a cultural inclination toward job stability in France, which can sometimes discourage individuals from pursuing entrepreneurial ventures. It also affects the investment decision-making process, as in France it is much easier to find investments for a development project rather than for a promising tech start-up.

Lack of information: While the French ecosystem offers a comprehensive approach to startups development, scale-ups, on the other hand, even promising ones, have problems with access to information. They are less visible to investors capable of investing in them. There is also an information gap between research carried out by laboratories and research groups on similar subjects, which prevents a synergy effect.

High costs: France's high quality of life comes with a cost. High prices for consulting and other professional services, high labor, profit and corporate taxes can be a burden for startups, especially in their early stages.

Opportunities

Internationalization: Internationalization is a significant opportunity for French entrepreneurs, and there are several programs and initiatives aimed at helping French startups expand their presence and operations on a global scale. The French government backed Business France Association and CCI support export promotion initiatives to help startups sell their products and services abroad. Export-oriented programs assist French entrepreneurs in identifying target markets, developing export strategies, and navigating trade regulations.

The French Tech Mission, part of the broader French Tech initiative, is designed to support French startups in their internationalization efforts. It provides a range of resources, including market insights, networking opportunities, and introductions to potential partners and investors abroad. French Tech Missions in various countries and regions help startups navigate the specific challenges and opportunities in those markets.

GreenTech and Sustainability: GreenTech and sustainability represent a growing opportunity in the French entrepreneurial ecosystem. Startups in this sector are working on innovative solutions to address environmental challenges, reduce carbon emissions, and promote sustainable practices across various industries. With government support, strong environmental regulations, and increasing consumer awareness, France is well-positioned to become a leader in GreenTech innovation and sustainability as France is committed to the goals of the Paris Agreement, which aims to limit global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius. This commitment creates a supportive environment for GreenTech and sustainability-focused startups.

The French government provides funding and incentives for GreenTech startups through various programs, including grants, subsidies, and tax credits. These financial incentives help accelerate

innovation and adoption of sustainable technologies. France is known for its investments into renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, and hydropower. Startups in this sector focus on innovative solutions for harnessing and managing renewable energy efficiently, Verkor being an iconic leader-startup to manufacture low-carbon batteries, targeting the electric mobility markets, having raised more than €3bln.

The GreenTech agenda has become a driver for the automotive industry in France, which is undergoing a transformation towards electric and hybrid vehicles. Startups are contributing to this shift by developing electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure, battery technologies, and EV-related services like vehicle sharing and ride-hailing.

Digital Transformation: The developing French entrepreneurial tech ecosystem provides a significant opportunity for digital transformation, leveraging digital technologies to revolutionize industries, enhance efficiency, and improve customer experiences. French industries such as manufacturing, healthcare, and agriculture are already undergoing digital transformations. Startups play a crucial role in modernizing these sectors by introducing technologies like IoT (Internet of Things), AI (Artificial Intelligence), and automation to increase efficiency and competitiveness.

The very important French textile sector can benefit from new tech solutions in online retail, payment processing, and customer experience optimization. French consumers increasingly prefer online shopping, providing opportunities for startups to develop new e-commerce solutions, and new solutions may reduce costs on clothes returns, increasing customer satisfaction and cutting down CO2 footprint.

Healthcare innovation: Recent global health challenges have underscored the importance of healthcare innovation. France, with its world-class healthcare system and research institutions, can capitalise on opportunities in biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, telemedicine, and healthcare data analytics. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of telemedicine in France. HealthTech startups enjoy special funding programs, creating digital healthcare solutions, including teleconsultation platforms, health monitoring devices, and AI-driven diagnostics, to improve access to healthcare services.

Improving institutional support: The rapidly developing start-up sector has shown the need to improve institutional support reducing its bias. At the same time, improving institutional support is a long-term endeavor that requires collaboration between government entities, educational institutions, industry associations, and the startup community. By addressing these areas, France can

create a more conducive environment for entrepreneurship, innovation, and business growth, ultimately strengthening its entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Expanding and simplifying access to grants and subsidies for scale-ups, especially in critical sectors like deep tech, sustainability, and healthcare, can boost the entrepreneurial ecosystem, as successful scale-ups act as role models for emerging start-ups.

Simplifying the process of registering and licensing businesses can reduce administrative burdens on startups and make it easier for them to establish themselves. Examining and adjusting regulations to be more accommodating to innovative business models and technologies will foster a more favourable business environment.

Right-skilling for women-led businesses: France has made progress towards gender equality over the past two decades, but significant gaps persist in workforce participation, leadership positions and pay. Major disruptions in the labor market have begun that could have profound implications for gender equality through 2030. Automation and artificial intelligence, for example, will displace many workers while, simultaneously, increasing investments, rising incomes or aging population trends will create new jobs that require skills in short supply. Depending on how it unfolds, the “future of work” could drive gender equality—or hinder it. The dynamics could favor women, and that many challenges can and should be turned into opportunities. The overall shifts could favor women in France by contributing to a slight improvement in female workforce participation. More important is that these shifts will present major new opportunities for women in some sectors that are likely to grow. For example, women are well-positioned in the growing health care and social assistance sector and will benefit from dominant positions in some of the sector’s occupations that will grow fastest, including health aides, therapists and physicians. To capture the growth opportunities in these sectors, they will need to master specific new skills and reorient their careers. Linear career paths may become a relic of the 20th century. The demand for three skill categories—technological, social and emotional and higher cognitive skills—should grow the most over the next decade. While women overall have great strengths in these categories, they lag men in others, such as advanced technological skills and haven’t yet captured their fair share of leadership positions. Women’s prospects are not as bright in some other sectors and occupations. In the professional, scientific and technical sectors, for example, women hold more than their current share in the overall workforce in occupations that we believe will shrink, such as clerical and office support, and are underrepresented in occupations likely to grow, such as computer engineering. To capture the growth opportunities in those sectors, they will need to master specific new skills and reorient their careers. Linear career paths may become a relic of the 20th century. Helping women gain the most valuable new skills—“right-skilling”—and ensuring that they are fairly represented in those efforts will require concerted actions by governments, educational institutions, companies and other public and private institutions. Leaders across these organizations will need to help their

stakeholders understand the importance of right-skilling for both women and men and create transparency about major shifts in demand for labor.

Threats

Regulatory hurdles: Regulatory hurdles pose significant challenges to startups and are considered a threat within the entrepreneurial ecosystem. While regulations are often designed to protect consumers, ensure fairness, and maintain market stability, they can inadvertently stifle innovation and hinder the growth of new businesses.

Regulatory frameworks in France can be complex, especially for startups with limited resources. Navigating these complexities requires legal expertise and can be not only time-consuming, diverting valuable resources away from product development and growth, but costly as well.

To address the threat of regulatory hurdles, it's crucial for France to strike a balance between consumer protection, economic growth, and innovation. This can involve ongoing regulatory reform efforts to simplify compliance processes, promote regulatory clarity, and support startups as they navigate the legal landscape. Collaboration between government entities, industry associations, and the startup community can help identify areas where regulations can be streamlined and made more conducive to innovation and entrepreneurship.

Traditional mindset: The traditional mindset, often characterized by risk aversion, a preference for job security, and a cultural emphasis on established career paths, can become a significant threat to the entrepreneurial landscape in France. France has strong laws defending workers. Together with traditional mindsets this factor often prioritizes job stability and the safety of established career paths. As a result, many individuals are hesitant to take the risks associated with entrepreneurship, which can involve financial insecurity and uncertainty.

Entrepreneurship is inherently uncertain, and startups often face unpredictable challenges. The traditional mindset's discomfort with uncertainty can deter individuals from pursuing entrepreneurial opportunities. Startups require a diverse range of talent, from technical experts to marketing professionals. The traditional mindset can make it difficult for startups to attract and retain skilled individuals who may prefer established, secure job opportunities.

Not only does traditional mindset affect entrepreneurial climate, it also limits available funding for start-ups as French VCs are more risk-averse than their US counterparts.

US VCs: Complicated regulations and risk-averse French VCs compel French start-ups to turn to the US capital. The willingness of U.S. venture funds to invest in French startups and take equity can be a risk within the French entrepreneurial landscape. When U.S. venture funds invest in French startups, they often seek equity stakes in exchange for their capital. This can dilute the ownership and control of the startup's founders and existing shareholders. While equity investment can provide funding, it also means sharing decision-making authority.

Equity investments from U.S. venture funds may come with expectations of technology and intellectual property transfer. Startups may need to share their innovations and proprietary technologies, potentially leading to loss of competitive advantage or control over their intellectual property.

U.S. venture funds often have shorter investment horizons and higher return expectations. This pressure for quicker exits can lead to premature decisions, such as selling the startup or going public before it has fully realised its growth potential. If U.S. venture funds become the dominant source of funding in the French startup ecosystem, it can lead to capital flight, where successful startups relocate to the United States to access a larger and more mature market.

Geopolitical risks: Political and economic instability in Europe or globally can impact the ease of doing business and international trade. Political and economic uncertainty, whether within Europe, in Africa or globally, can affect start-up strategies of development, and even their solutions as France has close historic ties and collaboration with a number of African countries.. Global trade disputes, tariffs, or changing regulations can pose challenges to startups, especially those with international ambitions.

Global competition: France faces fierce competition from established entrepreneurial ecosystems worldwide, particularly from Silicon Valley, China, and other European countries. These ecosystems have deep pools of talent, access to substantial venture capital, and a track record of successful startups, making it challenging for France to compete on a global scale.

Brain Drain: France has historically faced the challenge of "brain drain" as talented individuals sometimes opt to pursue opportunities in more established entrepreneurial ecosystems. This can weaken the local talent pool and reduce the innovation potential of the ecosystem.

To succeed in the face of these opportunities and threats, the French entrepreneurial ecosystem must continue its efforts to attract and retain talent, foster innovation, simplify regulations, and support startups as they navigate global competition and economic uncertainties. Adapting to the

changing landscape and leveraging its strengths will be essential for the ecosystem's sustained growth and competitiveness.

Ireland

SWOT Analysis

Below we present in the form of brief postulates. The validation of each of them following a methodical approach would, however, lie outside the scope of the ExcEllent project and in this respect is not necessary. In any case, and counting on the fact that the aim of the project is to capitalize on ‘unstructured entrepreneurial experiences, stories and narratives’, we see that each mentioned SWOT adds value to the project and may substantially help in finding new ways of conceptualising and promoting entrepreneurship – or to use a term we mentioned before – *‘help organisations walk the extra mile’ into their every-day practices and policies.*

Fig 13 SWOT Matrix showcasing the key factors shaping Bulgaria's entrepreneurial landscape

Strengths

- Ireland has a *business model of substance* with depth, diversity, and *years of tactical policy planning and implementation behind it*.
- Ireland has a diversity of industries which do R&D and high-value manufacturing and generates indigenous firms of scale with outward investment.
- Ireland is resilient enough to have emerged strongly from the recent global recession with the highest growth and population rates in the European Union²⁸.
- Ireland possesses a unique position as a global hub, where top international companies locate their headquarters, but also in terms of attracting highly talented and young researchers and scientists who see the opportunity in having ease of access to global markets.
- Irish entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystems can be 'fed' from both the supply and the demand side namely by young and eager to succeed researchers, scientists and professionals many of which have a different background and nationality than the Irish, as well international corporations and a long-established, multi-faceted and stable access to North America corporate, academic and research communities.
- Successful combination of 'a new sense of initiative' and factors such as low taxation, pro-business regulatory policies, and a young, tech-savvy workforce.
- Willingness and competence of government and administration authorities like Enterprise Ireland as well as other stakeholders like research performing organisations and universities to *walk the extra mile and find solutions that make things work*. This is something that cannot be found in other countries as widely openly and freely available, and this is also the reason for another strength:
- Researchers and scientists, especially those coming from other EU and non-EU countries find it easier to build their own enterprise in Ireland than in other countries of the EU.

Weaknesses

Several weaknesses that appear in other countries fortunately do not hold for the case of Ireland. Some other factors that might appear as weaknesses like e.g. the fact that Ireland has a smaller economy when compared to other EU countries, or the relatively small population size, are not to be

²⁸ IBEC Report: Ireland: A model of Substance, not dated, <https://www.ibec.ie/-/media/documents/ibec-campaigns/campaign---substance/six-characteristics-of-substance.pdf>

considered seriously as weaknesses when considering a pan-European or global market setting. However, this does not mean that there are no weaknesses to mention at all:

- Despite its openness and the indisputable advantage of ‘making things work’ and ‘walking the extra mile’, there is a deficit – not only in Ireland but same as in almost every other EU country – related to *the need for strong networking and for entrepreneurs to build and operate their own business networks at national and regional level* to seek for advice and support and facilitate access to funding, investors, opportunities, markets and customers. One may see this as a particular national ‘thing’ in each country of the EU, however it is something that can be counterbalanced eventually by the creation of a European entrepreneurial identity. This is what we aspire with ExcellEnt to find inspiration for coming up with new ways of foundations for visions of our common European future.
- Another weakness relates to the relatively high costs for running a company and acquiring services. More specifically, in the ‘Cost of Doing Business in Ireland’ issued in April 2019 that has been commissioned by the Irish National Competitiveness Council appears an interesting diagram (pg. 48) presenting the comparison of services producer prices for the year 2017. The source of the figure is the Eurostat Services producer prices - annual data and the case that is demonstrated there is that ‘when compared to other EU countries, services prices are rising relatively quickly in Ireland, with Luxembourg being the only economy measured where services prices increased faster than Ireland. In Denmark, services producer prices declined since 2015, and are now²⁹ around 4.5% lower than they were in 2015. The report also mentions that ‘the cost profile of Ireland can be described as ‘high cost, slowly increasing’ and in this regard, Ireland finds itself in the company of countries like Iceland, Denmark and Sweden. The slow growth in costs – and particularly the fact that it is well below comparator countries - is welcome from a cost competitiveness perspective’.
- In 2019 Ireland had the fifth lowest social security costs as a percentage of personnel costs in the EU27 (10.7%) . In the same year Sweden reported the highest proportion of personnel costs related to social security (31.7%). Bulgaria, Greece and France to name three other countries that we have partners from in the ExcellEnt project, appear far above (France with 28.2%) and quite much above (Greece with 20% and Bulgaria with 14.8%). Keeping social security costs low may have been historically a key element to attract investments but in the long run may raise

²⁹ To be noticed: figures are of 2017.

questions. Of course, from the narrow ‘win by all means’ perspective of the entrepreneurs this might not appear as a weakness though in the long run it definitely is.

Opportunities

- Improved access to funding instruments and support measures, especially and mainly if there are preexisting and / or longstanding links with the Irish higher education and research ecosystems. This opportunity pairs also with the opportunity of facing relatively reduced difficulties associated with accessing finance.
- Use of new and emerging technologies to reduce input costs, increase efficiency and add value to the particular core business. While this opportunity may strongly vary from one application area or market domain to another, it definitely increases value for carrying out an entrepreneurial activity in the Republic than in some other country of the Union. This opportunity also pairs with the opportunity of taking advantage of diversification including further development of the green, the circular and bio-economy.
- Open access to new markets and / or expand access to existing markets. Ireland for historic reasons may help innovations to travel from and to North America, same as it offers the opportunity to build bridges for access to investors from North America and explore the development of markets to both sides of the Atlantic.
- This is not an Irish-only opportunity as it can easily get adapted to each country participating in the ExcEllent project and appearing in the present report. However it is important and therefore mentioned separately: exploit and build on national capacities that will allow for faster business development than in other countries. This opportunity also pairs with the opportunity of capitalising on the increased market opportunities accessible from Ireland and the enhanced speed and process of knowledge transfer that characterizes the Irish higher education and research ecosystems.

Threats

Entrepreneurship is shaped following international patterns – and these are not anymore property of some market or country but there is an increased – or more specifically: *threateningly* increased – osmosis of trends that appear all over the EU and globally. To this context, the unique characteristics related historically to the ‘celtic tiger’ may in the future appear as characteristics of other countries and regions that aim to take a leading position and attract entrepreneurs. However, there is no need

to see the rise of new ‘tigers’ as a threat for the Irish ecosystem at all, as there is space for co-existence and synergies. This is also the aim of projects like ours namely to develop a new level of understanding for ‘unstructured entrepreneurial experiences, stories, narratives’ and come up with new models for addressing the challenge of (self)employability.

To our opinion, the biggest threat is, believe it or not, not related with the rise of new competitors that will offer same or similar products or services. *The biggest threat relates to the ‘loss of the walk the extra mile’ culture that distinguishes Ireland and the Irish ecosystem; this might bring the mentality of finding solutions to problems and making things work to extinction. Such a development would result to a failure to support what we praised Ireland for deploying a ‘business model of substance’.*

Contributing factors to the above may be found in many reasons and the potential trajectories to failure will be supported by several interpretation paths. However. It is important to understand the size of the threat and its impact to the real economy of Ireland. Especially in the services sector, the absence of (high) quality services is severe though difficult for the people to conceptualise or imagine till it is very late.

Ukraine

SWOT Analysis

Figure 14: SWOT matrix showcasing the key factors shaping Ukraine’s entrepreneurial landscape

Strengths

Ukraine possesses a blend of competitive advantages that, with a strategic and skilled approach, have the potential to drive significant economic growth.

1. Geographical location and logistical possibilities, access to the sea

Ukraine is located at the confluence between Europe and Asia, very close to several countries belonging to the European Union. Ukraine has 18 commercial ports on the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov, which are currently threatened in the context of the 2022 war, due to their strategic position and their crucial role in the national economy.

2. Significant natural resources

Ukraine is a country of significant agricultural production, particularly wheat, sunflower and beetroot. The country has a dense network of oil and gas pipelines which notably allow Russia to transport its products to Europe. This network and these resources are one of the keys to the 2022 war.

3. Qualified human capital

This is not so much about the fact that Ukrainian labor migrants are in demand abroad, but about the presence in Ukraine of a good system of technical education and scientific base in general.

4. Developed IT and Tech sectors

The tech sector has been a bright spot in the Ukrainian economy, creating high-paying jobs and attracting hundreds of millions of dollars in foreign investment.

The war has not slowed the success of Ukraine's IT sector which is seeing 20% growth in 2022 ³⁰. From artificial intelligence, blockchain, FinTech to software development and more, Ukraine has over 300,000 IT specialists, and is at the forefront of developments in the industry, with IT outsourcing Ukraine's third largest export.

5. A large capacity and virtually unlimited domestic market

³⁰ «Investing and doing business in Ukraine», CMS, <https://cms.law/en/media/local/cms-cmno/files/publications/other/investing-and-doing-business-in-ukraine-2022-2023?v=2>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

The global market of Ukraine is the goal of 63% of startups, 24% are focused only on the local market, and just 12% are focused on the external market. This means that Ukrainian startups consider the Ukrainian market as a potential market for testing their product and their idea ³¹.

6. Creative and innovative business ideas

The main capital of Ukrainian startups is the talent of their founders, valued and sought after by many foreign companies.

7. Resilience and agility

Ukrainian businesses are also displaying extraordinary resilience in the face of great pressure. Such resilience is highlighted by the 70% of Ukrainian businesses that are continuing to operate, despite the invasion of their country. 63% of businesses have also been able to retain most, if not all, of their staff. Agility is also in abundance among Ukrainian businesses, for despite having to face two unforeseen events, first the Covid-19 pandemic and then the war, and yet were still able to pivot and adapt.

Despite the extremely difficult conditions and unstable situation, according to the EBA, 76% of entrepreneurs plan to expand their business, of which:

- 28% aim to expand their geographical presence;
- 26% plan to open new business areas;
- 25% want to change their strategy to the foreign market;
- 21% - will increase the number of employees ³².

8. Regulatory procedures

Simplified tax system. Enterprises in the so-called “3rd group” of taxation, with a turnover of 5 million UAH per year, pay only 5% of the gross income tax (with an option of 2% during the war status).

Digitalization. The application Diia.City, set up by the Ukrainian government during the pandemic, and widely used during the current war, helps entrepreneurs citizens handle their legal and tax

³¹ «Business in times of war: Ukrainian perspective», Payoneer, <https://www.payoneer.com/resources/research-reports/business-times-of-ukrainian-war/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

³² «How does Ukrainian business survive the war», Visit Ukraine, <https://visitukraine.today/blog/1810/how-does-ukrainian-business-survive-the-war/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

issues online. Opening a small and medium business in Ukraine, as well as sale of business and re-registration is made fairly quickly.

9. Low cost of goods/ services

Cheap labour market. Doing business in Ukraine is beneficial for business owners, as the average wage in the country is about 10,000 UAH.

Low prices for raw materials make the processing and production of goods in Ukraine profitable.

Weaknesses

1. High level of corruption

Corruption and embezzlements continue to significantly affect the country. While President of Ukraine Zelensky has implemented robust anti-corruption measures, particularly targeting civil servants, progress in tackling corruption remains limited, posing a major challenge in Ukraine.

2. Bureaucracy and barriers from the side of regulatory and fiscal authorities

Pronounced bureaucracy, a high level of the shadow economy, unpredictable actions of the state affecting the business - are the main obstacles for the economy development. High administrative burden on business, complex tax procedures and tax audits, high interest rates on loans, delayed logistics in the borders add to the above and act as the principal brake for foreign investors.

As of today, Ukraine has just under 1,000 instruments of state regulation of business, which tie the hands of entrepreneurs who are trying to survive and maintain their own business on a daily basis.

3. Lack of a well-established market economy and an accompanying development strategy

The Ukrainian economy is fragile and not very dynamic. Its GDP has undergone major fluctuations since the country's independence in 1991, falling by more than half during the last decade of the 20th century, then recording a recurrent decline. This decline is a brake for investors, which adds to the political instability of the area and limits potential investments.

4. Lack of strong institutions

The weaknesses in state institutions and the absence of standardized rules for all participants in the economy, give rise to issues related to the functionality of law enforcement and judicial systems,

state regulation, and inequality before the law. Formal institutions may be related to corrupt practices, which in its turn reduces trust to the government.

The progress achieved in the reforms that have been initiated, including in the judicial system, which is particularly in need of reform, and in the banking system, still falls far short of the set goals.

5. Low purchasing power

According to the Ministry of Social Policy, in 2022 the number of Ukrainians living below the poverty line increased to almost 30%, which in turn had a significant impact on the solvency of citizens, with consumer inflation reaching 26.6%³³.

6. Shortage of skilled professionals and population decline

Many high tech employees fled the country at the outbreak of the war, with many unlikely to return for the foreseeable future. mobilization of employees and related difficulties in going on short-term business trips abroad, booking employees, and staff turnover.

7. Difficult access to foreign investments and international programs

The most frequently indicated external development barrier was a problematic access to external financing.

Among other problems related to financing are few active local funds, not enough foreign VC funds with offices in Ukraine, few angel investors with relevant experience

8. Limitation or lack of financial or other support on the governmental level

Despite challenging working conditions, government support programs still do not enjoy widespread popularity among SME representatives. For example, 24% of entrepreneurs lack information about government and international support programs. At the same time, entrepreneurs have actively utilized tax incentives (38% of respondents) and the “Affordable Loans 5-7-9%” program (28%). Entrepreneurs complained about difficulties obtaining the loan, high initial contributions, unexplained rejections, and the program’s limited coverage of many business categories³⁴.

9. Absence of development and educational services

³³ Ibidem.

³⁴ «Despite the growing financial losses, Ukrainian SMEs continue to pay salaries and support the Armed Forces of Ukraine», EBA, <https://eba.com.ua/en/msb-prodovzhuyut-vyplachuvat-zarplaty-ta-pidtrymuvaty-zsu-popry-zrostannya-finansovyh-vtrat/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

Many founders face a lack of basic knowledge and, as a result, don't know how to start and structure their work on a startup and how to raise their first capital. According to the PUSB research, almost 50% of interviewed entrepreneurs lack appropriate knowledge/skills/competencies within the team, and 55% of them have problems with the resources for competence. This results from absence of state programs for the development of SMEs and even absence of such a discipline as "entrepreneurship" in the school curriculum, and insufficient number of programs at universities to support and fund entrepreneurial ideas ³⁵.

10. Other ecosystem bottlenecks:

- lack of collaboration among stakeholders
- low connectivity with global markets - low overall connectivity of inflows of goods and services (especially financial) with other global hubs, as leading tech countries are much more connected than the rest of the world
- low demand of technologies on a domestic level
- low level of digitalization of Ukrainian companies prevent some companies to more readily acquire new products and technologies from startups.
- weak infrastructure and not developed enough support infrastructure
- not enough expertise and connections to help startups scale.
- minimal support to turn ideas into business - lack of strong mentorship and acceleration programs for early stage startups
- lack of entrepreneurial culture

Opportunities

Ukraine is currently invaded by Russia, and subject to intensive bombardments, resulting in destruction and deaths. Nevertheless, Ukraine enjoys massive support from almost all other states, whether it is Europe, the United States, or even China. The February-March 2022 war led to incredible outpourings of solidarity in favor of Ukrainian exiles (especially in Poland), as well as in favor of the country. Capital movements and international donations of food, arms or clothing are

³⁵ «Ukrainian Startup Ecosystem: facing the challenges, seizing the opportunities», Report by Polish-Ukrainian Startup Bridge, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18ZRdeTdrVilaejLgsODOQpgR3JgCnsEa/view?usp=drivesdk>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

innumerable. The duration of the conflict and its outcome are obviously key data, but it is possible to imagine that Ukraine will continue to enjoy major support from the rest of the world against Russia.

1. Financing, investments, international programs

The European and international community has pledged over USD 1trn in investment and aid for Ukraine, and the government is implementing investor-friendly reforms at a faster pace than ever before. Roads, airports, ports, hospitals, railways, rolling stock, telecommunications, energy, financial services sector. Efforts by the Ukrainian government, along with international support, to stabilize the situation, attract foreign direct investment, and implement economic reforms can contribute to gradually improving the investment attractiveness of the country over time.

Despite the war, 91% of the EBA companies plan to continue working in the Ukrainian market, and 55% will invest in Ukraine even during wartime, namely, in the agricultural sector, energy, IT and telecom, construction, pharmaceuticals, FMCG, real estate, and others. Besides, 12% believe that it will be profitable for new investors to enter Ukraine this year, although 57% of respondents hesitate³⁶.

2. European Union membership

The European Union has granted Ukraine candidate state status and Ukraine has completed 72% of its E.U. market-integration agreements. Possible post-conflict membership of the European Union is for example envisaged, which would allow Ukraine to benefit from better political stability and boost its economy³⁷.

3. Convergence towards the EU Market

³⁶ «Ukraine's investment attractiveness index falls to its lowest since 2013», EBA, <https://eba.com.ua/en/indeks-investytshjnoyi-pryvablyvosti-ukrayiny-pokazav-najnyzhche-znachennya-z-2013-roku/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

³⁷ «Ukraine's government announced that it fulfilled 72% of all obligations under the Ukraine-EU Association agreement», European Pravda, <https://www.eurointegration.com.ua/eng/news/2023/03/24/7158599/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

Convergence towards the European market is vital for Ukrainian startups and is directly linked to the need for better connections to investor networks and will shift collaboration between the ecosystems on a new level ³⁸.

- Ratifying the so-called “transport visa-free regime” will allow for Ukrainian carriers’ bilateral and transit traffic in European countries without the need to obtain special permits and international driver’s licenses.
- Another step in simplifying trading conditions with the EU states was joining the “customs visa-free regime,” i.e., a common transit regime allowing a vehicle to have a single declaration and guarantee for the export, import, and transit of goods.
- An equally important European integration document is the Common Aviation Area Agreement, allowing Ukraine make domestic and complex flights within the EU
- The number of countries with which Ukraine has a free trade zone increased by one last year after Turkey joined in. Therefore, Ukraine currently has free trade agreements with 45 countries.
- Another four laws enhance national property rights protection legislation, which is a priority for the European Union. Two documents deal with the protection of property rights for geographical brands

4. Structural reforms

The Ukrainian government has launched a number of reforms, required to open formal accession negotiations with the EU, including strengthening the judiciary and abandoning the oligarchic system, as well as simplifying the tax system.

Initiatives such as deregulation and funding programs contribute to a more favorable environment for new business ventures improving the business climate and supporting entrepreneurship.

The after-war period should prioritise focusing on further provisions and practical implementation of judicial, anti-oligarchical, media and other institutional reforms.

³⁸ «Reforms in the war year: nine areas that underwent the most change in 2022», Vox Ukraine, <https://voxukraine.org/en/reforms-in-the-war-year-nine-areas-that-underwent-the-most-change-in-2022>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

If Ukraine finally introduces all the expected changes and reforms, it may become the most attractive country in Europe for impact investors.

5. Business reconstruction and reformation

Despite ongoing hostilities, businesses, for the first time since the start of the full-scale war, said they expected a rebound in business activity over the next 12 months

The ongoing crisis has also given Ukrainian businesses a huge blow and forced them to rapidly adjust and be highly resilient to the new realities. Testament to this quick adaptation and resilience is that 70% of Ukrainian SMBs, despite everything, were largely able to achieve business continuity, 83% were able to retain all or most of their employees, and 38% are looking to hire more this year. And all this, despite 72% not having a business crisis plan in place before the war broke out ³⁹.

6. Talents

Ukraine is known for its highly skilled and educated workforce, particularly in technical fields such as IT, engineering, and sciences. The country has a strong system of higher education institutions and technical schools that produce graduates with relevant skills and knowledge. This talent pool provides a solid foundation for entrepreneurial ventures, especially in sectors that require specialized expertise.

Ukrainian universities and educational institutions have been increasingly emphasizing entrepreneurship-focused programs and courses, providing entrepreneurs with the necessary knowledge, skills, and mindset to start and manage their businesses.

7. Military tech sector

Ukraine has become a significant player in the field of military technology, with Ukrainian innovators and tech companies leading the way in developing cutting-edge advancements. Initiatives like BRAVE1 have fostered collaboration between the government, military, and private sector to address defence issues and create innovative military technologies ⁴⁰.

³⁹ «Business in times of war: Ukrainian perspective», Payoneer, <https://www.payoneer.com/resources/research-reports/business-times-of-ukrainian-war/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

⁴⁰ «Ukraine's tech sector playing vital wartime economic and defence role», Atlantic Council, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/ukrainealert/ukraines-tech-sector-is-playing-vital-wartime-economic-and-defense-roles/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

Ukraine's involvement in military technology also holds immense potential for the country's postwar recovery. The experience gained by Ukrainian tech companies in the defence tech sector positions them as leaders in the industry. As Ukraine's tech industry emerges from the war, it will enjoy an enhanced global reputation, attracting interest and collaboration from countries worldwide.

The expertise and solutions developed by Ukrainian specialists in military technology will be in high demand, further driving economic growth and improving national security.

8. Demand for Ukrainian technologies and startups

Ukraine has a burgeoning tech sector with a pool of talented engineers and developers, which has attracted attention from international investors and companies.

- the tech sector has not just survived but thrived: by the end of 2022, Ukraine's IT exports had grown nearly 7 per cent, even as the economy shrunk by almost a third. The experts are predicting the Ukrainian economy will bounce back and that the investment made today will bring dividends for years to come ⁴¹.
- Ukraine has seen a rise in the number of successful startups and tech companies in various sectors such as fintech, e-commerce, software development, and artificial intelligence. These success stories have boosted the country's reputation as an innovation hub and attracted the attention of international investors

Overall, Ukrainian technologies and startups are gaining momentum and recognition in the global tech scene. With their technical expertise, cost-effectiveness, and government support, Ukrainian startups are well-positioned to continue attracting demand and making a mark in the international market.

9. High national unity

The world has learned of the determination and resilience of Ukrainians in the defence of their country. Its industries, its SMEs, and its skilled and educated workforce are just as resilient. Over three million Ukrainians have returned home since Russia's invasion in February. Businesses are open, people are working ⁴².

⁴¹ «The remarkable resilience of Ukrainian tech sector», Wired, <https://www.wired.com/story/ukraine-startups-resilience-tech-sector/>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

⁴² «Investing and doing business in Ukraine», CMS <https://cms.law/en/media/local/cms-cmno/files/publications/other/investing-and-doing-business-in-ukraine-2022-2023?v=13>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

Threats

1. Ongoing russia's military aggression with undefined termination period

The country is currently in fire and blood, ruined and besieged. This is of course the main threat, both to people and to infrastructure, exports and the economy. At the end of the conflict, the country will probably have to be completely rebuilt, as the destruction is so extensive.

2. Economic challenges

Since the beginning of the full-scale invasion, the Ukrainian economy and business have suffered a devastating blow and faced economic difficulties, such as inflation, currency fluctuations, and a high poverty rate, affecting the purchasing power of consumers, lower demand for goods and services. 30.4% is an unprecedented decline in Ukraine's national economy in 2022, and at the start of 2023 the situation has only been getting worse as Ukraine's power and heating infrastructure have been targeted ⁴³.

Among other related outcomes affecting entrepreneurship:

- destroyed capacities, mine-studded fields;
- destroyed logistics routes, a shortage of vehicles and a significant increase in fuel prices;
- a significant increase in prices for energy, raw materials and supplies;
- occupation of some territories, which temporarily deprived companies of access to their production facilities and warehouses;
- loss of companies and partner countries;
- loss of opportunity to conduct almost any foreign economic activity due to the limited capacity of the country's western borders, almost completely paralyzed seaports, and closed borders with Russia and Belarus.

3. Electricity outages

Constant attacks on Ukraine's energy system in 2022 have led to frequent and prolonged power outages. According to the EBA statistics, 89% of private companies and state-owned enterprises felt

⁴³ «How does Ukrainian business survive the war», Visit Ukraine, <https://visitukraine.today/blog/1810/how-does-ukrainian-business-survive-the-war>,(accessed September 25, 2023).

the effects of Russia's strikes on the energy sector. Businesses have been forced to look for alternative sources of electricity and increase their spending on transport and consumables. In addition, the reduction in productive hours and the constant interruption of work processes have had a significant impact on companies' revenues ⁴⁴.

The approaching heating season of 2023 and possibility of further attacks on critical facilities might put at risk the existence of small businesses.

4. Loss of workforce, migration, brain drain

Labor migration deprives the country of highly qualified personnel and labor, and also narrows domestic demand. An additional challenge is a particular risk to male founders who might be drafted into the military. This situation severely hampers their ability to travel abroad to promote their startups and seize opportunities, thereby affecting both the growth prospects of these startups and investor confidence.

5. Combination of new reforms and war on the territory of the country

According to experts, the latest reforms promised by the government as an option to improve the economic system are currently very imperfect. Among its shortcomings, one can name insufficient determination, excessive tax burden - this especially applies to small business entities, whose incomes are not too large anyway.

6. Insecurity of investments

Insecurity of investments in Ukraine has been a concern due to various factors, not even mentioning the main and obvious country's state of war.

Political instability, corruption, legal and regulatory uncertainties, Perception and reputational risks, Weak rule of law, etc. require implementation of various reforms and providing constant and systematic changes.

7. Complete dependence on external financing

Reliance on external financing makes the Ukrainian economy highly susceptible to global economic downturns and fluctuations. Excessive borrowing to finance government expenditures or support the economy can lead to a debt crisis, higher interest rates, and reduced availability of credit for

⁴⁴ Ibidem.

entrepreneurs, making it more difficult for them to start or expand their businesses. Diversification of funding sources, fostering domestic investment, and addressing structural issues are essential to reduce these threats

8. Cybersecurity risks

Ukraine has been a target of cyberattacks in recent years, which can pose a significant threat to businesses. Cybersecurity vulnerabilities can lead to data breaches, financial losses, and reputational damage for entrepreneurs.

9. Global economic changes

- overall transition from globalism to national protectionism
- climate change and environmental concerns:
- financial instability and credit crunch:
- decrease in global demand for biofuels and decrease of export volumes of certain agricultural crops from Ukraine.
- technological advancements and automation
- trade wars and protectionism
- new war conflicts

Comprehensive Evaluation and Support Recommendations

Global SWOT Analysis based on the 6 National SWOT analysis

- **Strengths:**

The European entrepreneurial ecosystem is diverse and dynamic, supporting various entrepreneurs (start-up, spin-off, women led businesses, self-entrepreneurs etc) in various sectors and domains. **The European Union (EU) and the assessed national governments has launched several initiatives** to foster the development of the ecosystems, such as La French Tech, Team Europe Initiatives, Erasmus+, EIT HEI Initiative, JRC STI for SDGs project, etc. **The entrepreneurs are active in all the economic sectors, social and environmental issues, such as education, health, energy, and circular economy.** The European entrepreneurs benefit from **a supportive policy environments, a strong research and education systems, a vibrant culture of innovation and creativity, and a growing network of partners and mentors** in their own countries.

- **Weaknesses:**

The European entrepreneurs face some challenges in **accessing finance, talent retention, scaling up, and internationalisation.** The entrepreneurs may encounter **language barriers and cultural differences with customers, investors, and partners** from other countries. They suffer from **bureaucracy, taxation, regulation, and competition issues that hamper their growth and innovation potentials.**

- **Opportunities:**

The European entrepreneurs can leverage the opportunities offered by the digital transformation, the green transition, and the European integration with new accession countries to create new solutions and markets. They benefit from the **increasing demand for social and environmental impact from consumers, investors, and policymakers.** They tap into the **enormous potential of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, biotechnology, and nanotechnology** to enhance their products and services.

- **Threats:**

European entrepreneurs face **increased competition from other countries and regions that have more developed or dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystems.** They may be affected by political, economic, social, or environmental uncertainties or crises that may disrupt their operations or markets. They may encounter **ethical, legal, or security risks related to their use or development of new technologies or data.**

Needs Assessment

- *Specific needs of each entrepreneurial ecosystem.*
- *Requirements for the ecosystem to reach its full potential.*
- *Areas where additional support or resources are required.*

Greece

The interplay between the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in Greece's entrepreneurial ecosystem offers a complex but navigable landscape. Leveraging strengths can act as a bulwark against threats. For instance, Greece's highly educated talent pool and international exposure can make its startups resilient against economic volatility and competitive global ecosystems. Similarly, government initiatives and collaborative networks may help in buffering against adverse policy shifts and the rapid pace of disruptive technologies.

Conversely, focusing on weaknesses can open up new opportunities. Streamlining bureaucratic hurdles can make emerging sectors like eHealth and EduTech more accessible, and resolving early-stage funding issues could pave the way for fruitful public-private partnerships. Meanwhile, Greece's EU membership provides a counterbalance to the small domestic market, offering broader avenues for growth. Essentially, a nuanced understanding of these interconnections can inform targeted strategies to fortify Greece's entrepreneurial ecosystem, making it both robust and adaptive.

Bulgaria

The Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem is a dynamic blend of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, all deeply interconnected. Bulgaria boasts a skilled tech talent pool and supportive government policies, positioning it well for sectors like biotech and robotics. Collaborations between academia and businesses can further drive innovation. However, challenges like demographic shifts and potential labour shortages, especially with the emigration of skilled professionals, pose risks. The gap between education and market needs can hinder startup growth. The digital transformation, enhanced by expanding digital infrastructure, can help bridge this gap. Leveraging EU funds can support startups and attract international talent. While the growth in the ICT sector is impressive, diversifying into other sectors is crucial for economic stability. The regulatory environment can either boost or hinder the ecosystem's growth. Ultimately, Bulgaria's entrepreneurial future depends on balancing these elements, ensuring growth and resilience.

Turkiye

The strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in Turkiye's entrepreneurial ecosystem offers a landscape where opportunities would be leveraged, and threats would be mitigated by the strengths of the ecosystem. Furthermore, proactive planning to overcome weaknesses can enable the ecosystem ready to leverage the opportunities and diminish the negative possible impacts of threats. For instance, Turkiye's young and educated population can mitigate the threats of brain drain and the risk of outflow of new startups from the country. Government initiative and novel support programs and legislations as strength and opportunity of the ecosystem can enhance the potential of the ecosystem to overcome threats emerging from economic volatility and investment squeeze. Turkiye's strong supportive infrastructure for entrepreneurs may buffer any threats that decrease investments to Turkish startups, but also may help in acting on rising awareness and usage of ICT. Such an infrastructure provides opportunities for entrepreneurs to start an ICT startup.

Acting on weaknesses, on the other hand, can open new opportunities. Streamlining bureaucratic hurdles and making regulations for the support of R&D and entrepreneurial activities much easier can increase the number of startups created and benefited from these support mechanisms, resolve early-stage funding issues and may lead to new innovations and public-private partnerships. Meanwhile, Turkish firms and startups' intentions to the application of emerging technologies and emergence of new hubs in new technologies can be a remedy of lower business and technology sophistication of Turkish industries. Understanding of these interconnections is useful to design targeted strategies to fortify the Turkish entrepreneurial ecosystem and ensure its sustainable development.

France

The conducted SWOT analysis exposes the cross-impact character of the French entrepreneurial system visualised in *Fig. 5*. Its interconnection is secured by the research methodology that allowed to leverage different data sources. France's entrepreneurial support ecosystem is coherent and government driven. Therefore, government initiatives and government-backed institutions impact all other players making it possible to turn weaknesses into opportunities by policy changes.

French entrepreneurial stakeholders constantly influence each other, startups infusing government agents with innovations, traditional big banks trying to embark on an agile path of development. The strong interconnection and cross-impact of the system often questions its duality, when on one

hand your opportunity of **internalisation** allows it to attract international talents, and on the other hands, when you remain open you see a threat of **brain drain**.

Ireland

There is definitely an obvious space for interplay amongst all SWOT components: what we mentioned before as strengths for the Irish entrepreneurial ecosystem may be substantially leveraged by reducing the presented weaknesses, the same as the importance of opportunities can be further leveraged by a reduction of the anticipated threats.

However, and same as in many (actually: in all) real world situations, the development of acerbic scenarios and thorough plans of action as part of a situation room analysis may not help us foresee the future. To this, it is better to invent the future such as by means of the ExcellEnt project than to predict it, in an attempt to paraphrase a famous quote attributed to Alan Kay.

In Ireland, same as in the other countries participating in the project and appearing in the report, entrepreneurial ecosystems offer ‘a complex but navigable landscape’ as our colleagues from the Institute of Entrepreneurship Development mention in their report for the Greek ecosystem.

The real challenge is to come up with prototypes of entrepreneurial instances which might offer some understanding on how trans-national and in this respect pan-European entrepreneurship can be substantiated.

The existence of a highly educated talent pool in countries like Greece or Türkiye that might result in brain drain should not be seen as a direct gain or a positive development for e.g. the Irish or the French ecosystem if seen from the EU perspective.

However, if this brain drain and highly educated talent pool would have remained in their countries and had been unable or facing severe difficulties to unleash their innovation potential and knowledge capital, the use of this ‘highly educated talent pool’ at some other country of the Union is certainly a positive outcome not only for the country but also for the Union at large.

The concept of ‘walking the extra mile(s)’ that we praised as unique for Ireland is not difficult to be faced in each country. Several bureaucratic hurdles that are mentioned in the cases of Türkiye and Greece as well as in the cases of Bulgaria and Ukraine, can be regarded either as systemic and endogenous and thus difficult or impossible to change at all or – if thinking outside the box – regarding them as ‘subject to (meaningful) change’.

Ukraine

DEREGULATION

- significant reduce of the state role in business
- sale of all "dead" state assets to entrepreneurs who will find a much better use for them (small privatization)
- fight against corruption, investment protection.

With the reduction of the powers of the state and its influence on the economy in Ukraine, the scale of corruption will begin to decrease, as officials will be deprived of areas of responsibility from which they used to withdraw funds for their own benefit.

GOVERNMENTAL SUPPORT

- tax benefits for the recovery of enterprises,
- overall reduce of the tax burden, in particular on the wage fund
- improve the accessibility of grant programs for business,
- personnel retraining programs
- digitization of business processes,

Supporting policies that draw on the entrepreneurial conditions of a region could be an effective strategy to enhance productive entrepreneurship but also incentivize entrepreneurship using market-based tools and regional advantages

EASE of doing business

- ease legislation for creating IT startups in Ukraine
- reduce the tax burden
- improve legislation for cross border transactions

LEGAL REFORM

- address current legal barriers that hinder the operations of venture capitalists and other stakeholders under Ukrainian law.
- focus on improving the business environment, combating corruption
- ensure the security of investments.

TALENT

- raise quality of available entrepreneurship education programs
- create flexible regulations for local and foreign talent
- provide regional access to high-quality training programs
- stimulate RD, necessary to develop IT industry in Ukraine

FUNDING

- create more opportunities to support the idea-stage startups and first-time founders with the validation phase
- increase number of angel investors, establishing education and awareness programs about role and importance, creating platforms where potential investors can connect, and policies providing incentives, such as tax benefits and co-investment schemes
- expand the Pre-seed, Series A and Beyond investment ecosystem, building investor networks, providing tailored financing programs, education on investor engagement, etc.
- stimulate foreign VC investment in Ukrainian tech companies

DEMAND

- increase the usage of digital tools within public authorities
- continue to increase export of Ukrainian IT products and services
- increase expenditures on IT in private sector

Capacity Assessment

- Current capacity and capabilities of each entrepreneurial ecosystem.

- Strengths that enable the ecosystem to meet its goals.
- Gaps in resources, infrastructure, or skills.

Greece

Capitalizing on Opportunities

The opportunity for blending traditional sectors with technology should not be overlooked. Programs to incubate startups that merge tech with sectors like tourism and agriculture could be highly effective. Furthermore, the focus on social entrepreneurship can be expanded to tap into international funds dedicated to social impact, thus making Greece a go-to destination for impact investing.

Recommendations:

- Industry leaders should establish incubators that specifically focus on tech-enabled traditional sectors.
- The Ministry of Finance should actively pursue making Greece eligible for international funds dedicated to social entrepreneurship.

Enhancing Performance

To boost overall performance, Greece should actively promote entrepreneurship through nationwide campaigns and incentives. Creating a culture of innovation can be fostered through hackathons, workshops, and incentivizing R&D initiatives. Moreover, mentorship programs should be institutionalized to provide startups with the guidance needed to scale effectively.

Recommendations:

- The government could launch nationwide campaignz promoting entrepreneurship, supported by private-sector sponsorships.
- Regular hackathons and workshops should be organized and sponsored by industry leaders to foster innovation.
- Elevate Greece and similar initiatives should create official mentorship networks for startups.

Bulgaria

Capitalizing on Opportunities

To capitalize on the opportunities within the Bulgarian entrepreneurial ecosystem, it's important to focus on underrepresented sectors like biotech, robotics, deep tech, etc., which hold significant growth potential. The expansion of digital infrastructure, especially in underserved regions, will pave the way for a more inclusive entrepreneurial environment. Furthermore, fostering stronger collaborations between academia and businesses can bridge the innovation gap, ensuring that research translates into market-ready solutions. Leveraging available EU funds and programs can provide the necessary financial impetus, while a streamlined regulatory framework tailored for startups can facilitate smoother business operations and growth.

Recommendations:

- Enhance collaboration between research institutions and businesses, leveraging the funding for sector-specific growth.
- Tap into underrepresented sectors highlighted in the Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization 2021-2027 [27] to diversify the entrepreneurial base.
- Simplify procedures for startups to access EU funds, ensuring they benefit from initiatives like the Seed / Acceleration and Start-Up Fund [37] and the Venture Capital Fund [38].

Enhancing Performance

To enhance its overall entrepreneurial landscape, Bulgaria needs to champion entrepreneurship via countrywide initiatives and rewards. Cultivating an innovative mindset can be achieved through events like hackathons, training sessions, and by encouraging research and development efforts. Additionally, formalizing mentorship schemes will equip startups with the essential guidance to grow and thrive.

Recommendations:

- The government should consider setting up dedicated National Innovation Centres in key cities. These centres can act as hubs for hackathons, training sessions, and R&D projects, bringing together startups, researchers, and industry experts.
- Incorporate entrepreneurship and innovation modules at all levels of education. This early exposure can inspire and equip the next generation of entrepreneurs with the skills and mindset needed.
- Offer tax breaks or grants for startups focusing on R&D, and provide additional financial incentives for established businesses that collaborate with startups or invest in innovative projects.

Turkiye

Strategic Avenues of Improvement

The strategic avenues of improvement within the Turkish startup ecosystem are intricately woven into its current successes and challenges, necessitating a nuanced and forward-looking approach to harness its full potential. The ecosystem, while having demonstrated substantial growth and international success, particularly in digital sectors, is confronted with a myriad of challenges that could impede its forward trajectory. These encompass aspects such as the exhaustion of international interest, macroeconomic and governance issues, and the potential exodus of startups and talent, all necessitating strategic interventions to sustain and enhance its growth trajectory.

Ensuring technological advancement is paramount to maintaining the momentum of the Turkish startup ecosystem. The country must not only keep pace with but also anticipate and lead in adopting innovations that will shape the future sectors suitable for startups. This involves the availability of modern infrastructure, such as a 5G network, and sustained government and corporate support for R&D to ensure that professionals remain abreast of new technologies. Furthermore, the internal market should be aligned with global technological and regulatory standards to continue serving as a viable staging ground for Turkish startups with globally applicable products and services.

Moreover, stabilizing the investment environment is crucial to attracting post-seed investment from both domestic and international investors. The global outlook on Turkey's investment climate, characterized by high inflation and exchange rate volatility, necessitates creating and maintaining

conditions that mitigate country risk and foster a stable investing environment, particularly for late-stage VCs. Addressing talent migration by implementing strategies to retain talent within the country and/or leverage the international Turkish talent pool is vital to sustaining the ecosystem's growth and innovation.

Recommendations:

-Enhancing Regulatory Frameworks: Developing and implementing regulatory frameworks conducive to startup growth and innovation, providing clarity and stability in the business environment.

-Global Market Alignment: Ensuring the internal market is aligned with global technological and regulatory standards facilitates Turkish startups to develop globally applicable products and services.

-Talent Development and Retention: Implementing policies and initiatives that foster talent development within the country and implement mechanisms to retain talent and mitigate the exodus of skilled professionals.

-Fostering International Partnerships: Establishing and strengthening international partnerships to facilitate knowledge exchange technological transfer and provide Turkish startups with avenues to explore and penetrate global markets.

France

Capitalizing on Opportunities

Tackling the talent shortage that impedes the development of French Tech is being solved through its **internalisation** approach. French Tech Visa remains a powerful tool to attract talent. Attracting foreign talent contributes to increasing diversity among tech leaders, tending to boost the performance of start-ups. Poorly diversified teams and networks are less creative and less able to understand potential markets.

France's ongoing **digital transformation** encourages the creation of disruptive technology startups. In 2019 Bpifrance launched the Deep Tech plan aiming to make France the leading European breeding ground for tech startups, ahead of the UK. The Program offers to promote entrepreneurship in universities and research centres, and to support researcher-entrepreneurs. France needs to build on by implementing a policy to promote and facilitate the creation of

innovative companies by researchers in public laboratories. More generally, encourage the establishment of a culture of dissemination of research in society and the economy.

Enjoying the central European location and a vibrant tech ecosystem, France should address the European market "as a domestic market", developing a special support program for startups that want to scale-up in Europe.

Enhancing Performance

Territories and local players in Nice, Paris, Saclay, Nantes or Valence in France, or Saarbrücken in the Emilia Romagna region and Campania (Naples), are keen to experiment with this approach, which is intended to be more widely adopted by consortium members.

The aim is to take part in this experiment, which will address access to information on investment opportunities with players in the investment industry in each country, particularly in France, and to set up use cases with corporate partners, and possible research collaborations (notably European projects).

This champion's league could be structured around step-by-step acceleration programs (matrix or mawahub model) where at each step potential stakeholders adapted to each project are met....

Ireland

Capitalizing on Opportunities

Ireland is a very open economy, exhibiting one of the highest shares in exporting of domestic value within the OECD. It also has unique characteristics of openness to trade and foreign direct investment offers enhanced opportunities for entrepreneurship.

To the latter, and with the country as a large net recipient of foreign direct investments (FDI) that is considered as a major driver of economic development for the country, there is an opportunity to identify and use positive spillovers for Irish SMEs. It is for this reason that participation in global value chains hosted domestically would make increased sense. Same also applies for capitalising on building and operating increased linkages between multinational firms based in Ireland and indigenous Irish SMEs which could be developed in a number of ways, with the role of scientific or research and innovation-driven entrepreneurship playing the role of a catalyst.

What might seem like a blind spot to this is the lack of some type of basic financial education with an emphasis on SME business owners and entrepreneurs that would strengthen the managerial and financial skills of small business owners and managers as well as of start-up entrepreneurs.

Enhancing Performance

SME and entrepreneurship performance varies spatially within Ireland with the start-up rates appearing at their highest in Dublin and Cork. SME innovation rates show a similar core periphery pattern as identified also in a report dating back to 2015 by Crowley, F., & McCann. This practically means that there are substantial differences in the quality of local entrepreneurship ecosystems across Ireland in terms of the degree to which they provide favorable institutional and access to resources conditions.

Areas of positive interventions and improvements may include amongst others the promotion of policy measures to increase the productivity of micro, small and medium sized SMEs, while, most importantly, increase the business start-up rate and the business dynamism that these may exhibit in their initial development phases.

Aspects such as the provision of equal opportunities for entrepreneurship across the population and addressing gaps in the self-employment and entrepreneurship activity rates of women, youth and migrants are not only important but of direct relevance to the ExcEllent project. Paraphrasing a quote of one of our interviewees (off record) 'start-up entrepreneurship should not be related with a white old(er) man or woman with a senior academic or research position profile' but should be promoted as a vital resource both for the economy and the society at large.

This means that scale up of micro-enterprises with an indigenous locally-trading and non exporting start-ups should be given same or similar importance, attention and resources for support as to potential deeptech unicorns, as the former might exhibit higher chances to increase the cohort of medium-sized enterprises of above the 50 employees threshold. Such an approach might also help address spatial disparities in entrepreneurship by strengthening local entrepreneurship ecosystem conditions for start-up and scale-up entrepreneurship.

Ukraine

Capitalizing on Opportunities

Capitalizing on entrepreneurial opportunities in Ukraine requires a combination of market knowledge, innovation, and strategic planning. The country's integration into the EU and global democratic community, the level of national spirit and global attention and interest to Ukraine, efforts in speedy improvement of the business environment, quick development of innovation and defence tech gives unprecedented opportunities for both global and local businesses:

- using Ukraine as a testbed for new technologies. Local legislation doesn't have severe and detailed regulations for new technologies yet, allowing for the freedom of creativity and bold experiments. Global international attention in case of success helps promote the success story and its further scaling globally.
- the country is in need not only to rebuild the old, but to create a brand and bold new. There is an acute need for mature frameworks that will allow accepting international capital and investment and turn ideas into reality.
- Skillful management of local resources, building partnerships with local stakeholders, investment into ecosystem growth and maturity, attracting local entrepreneurs and their ideas, shaping it in the productive and effective way is the key to a global success.

Enhancing Performance

In order for startups to thrive in Ukraine, they require comprehensive support at both the early and later stages of their development. This assistance must be systematically implemented, relying on credible data rather than mere opinions.

The shortage of essential skills within the team and the inability to financially support employee competence development present significant hurdles. In startups, where innovation is supreme, knowledge and competences serve as the foundation for the company.

To foster the growth of young enterprises, it is crucial to establish an environment that facilitates continuous competence acquisition at each stage.

- integrating entrepreneurship into curricula, to help students develop essential skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity, which are crucial for entrepreneurial success ⁴⁵.
- aspiring entrepreneurs with a deep understanding of global ecosystems and how they function.
- establishing On-campus startup studios and incubation programs on educational campuses provides a nurturing environment for aspiring entrepreneurs.
- Enhancing Communication Channels for showcasing the Ukrainian innovation ecosystem on a global scale.
- provide availability of competent managers and quality of management education

⁴⁵ Ibidem.

Matchmaking Suggestions

- *Based on the SWOT analysis, needs, and capacity assessments, propose matchmaking suggestions for each entrepreneurial ecosystem.*
- *Recommend relevant stakeholders, partners, or resources across Europe that can provide support and collaboration opportunities.*

Greece

Collaboration can act as a catalyst for the Greek startup ecosystem. Greece should leverage platforms like Elevate Greece for local networking and consider creating alliances with other entrepreneurial hubs across Europe. Partnerships with academic institutions and industry leaders in maritime and energy sectors can also foster knowledge exchange and technical collaboration. These interactions can help Greek startups access wider markets and also bring in diverse expertise into the local ecosystem.

Recommendations:

- Elevate Greece and other similar initiatives should seek partnerships with similar organizations across Europe.
- Universities should collaborate with startups for R&D, facilitated by a liaison office established by the government.

Bulgaria

Matchmaking and collaboration are pivotal for the evolution of Bulgaria's entrepreneurial ecosystem. The institutions, businesses, and universities are disconnected, which hampers effective technology and knowledge transfer. To remedy this, the forthcoming Law on the Promotion of Research and Innovation (ZNNII) [35] proposes measures to foster collaboration, emphasizing the importance of synchronizing sectoral policies and promoting inter-institutional partnerships. This intertwining aims to cultivate an entrepreneurial culture, where startups can seamlessly access and leverage scientific research and technological advancements. Furthermore, the establishment of a National Innovation Fund and the Operational Program "Innovation and Competitiveness" (OPIC) 2021-2027 [36], which provides financial instruments like the Acceleration and Seed Fund and the Venture Capital Fund, are instrumental in fostering a supportive financial environment for startups.

This, coupled with the Business Booster online platform [25], facilitates knowledge sharing and networking among entrepreneurs, thereby nurturing a collaborative and innovative business landscape in Bulgaria.

Recommendations:

- Prioritize the swift implementation of the Law on the Promotion of Research and Innovation (ZNNII) [35] to establish clear mechanisms fostering innovation and collaboration.
- Facilitate platforms or initiatives that actively promote matchmaking between institutions, businesses, and universities to drive effective technology and knowledge transfer.
- Invest in training and capacity-building programs that equip stakeholders with the skills and knowledge to navigate and benefit from a collaborative entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Turkiye

The potential for further integration with the European startup ecosystem could be a pivotal element in leveraging the inherent advantages within the Turkish startup ecosystem. This integration provides a platform for Turkish startups to explore and penetrate international markets and facilitates a conduit for knowledge exchange, technological transfer, and collaborative innovation.

Global expansion and international recognition of Turkish startups have paved the way for entrepreneurs to explore opportunities in international markets, fostering an environment conducive to international collaborations and partnerships. The success stories of Turkish startups in international markets have inspired entrepreneurs within the country and garnered the attention of international investors and corporations, thereby opening avenues for collaborative ventures, investments, and partnerships.

Moreover, the technological advancements and innovations within the Turkish startup ecosystem provide a fertile ground for collaborative opportunities in research and development, technological transfer, and innovation.

Recommendations:

-Fostering International Partnerships: Establishing and strengthening international partnerships and collaborations to facilitate knowledge exchange technological transfer and provide Turkish startups with avenues to explore and penetrate global markets.

-Enhancing Global Presence: Implementing initiatives and platforms that enhance the global presence of Turkish startups, thereby attracting international investors, partners, and collaborators.

-Collaborative Innovation Hubs: Establishing collaborative innovation hubs that bring together startups, investors, and corporations from various countries to collaborate, innovate, and develop solutions to global challenges.

-International Startup Exchanges: Implementing international startup exchange programs that allow startups to explore and understand international markets, thereby fostering an environment conducive to international collaborations and partnerships.

France

French **innovation and tech hubs** act as a platform for matchmaking between startups, and startups and industries. While the existing matchmaking activities and pitching Demo Days spread across the country, trying to connect startups with industries and investors, France still has to develop and firmly establish collaboration practices between academia, startups and industries. This will enable to bridge the information gap that exists in France connecting the much needed academic research and laboratory facilities with the needs of industries.

Ireland

As far as aspects related to collaborative opportunities as result of matchmaking is concerned, the aforementioned OECD report suggests that a closer study of clusters in other EU countries such as the go-cluster for Germany and the Cluster Excellence Denmark in Denmark should be considered. The aim is to effectively facilitate and promote collaborations between large(r) enterprises and Irish start-ups and SMEs. The usual path chosen with e.g. online platforms and matchmaking events is only one option and not necessarily the best. There is much groundwork that is necessary before a matchmaking and also afterwards in all the necessary follow-ups that may increase the collaboration potential and make things happen. Again it is the 'walk the extra mile' mentality that might provide an advantage in terms of facilitating matchmaking within clusters and enable participating entrepreneurs to become familiar with each other's strengths and business models. This might, apart from increasing the quality of enterprise-led networks, and catering for easier access to and support for formalising network structures, it could also facilitate cross-enterprise and enterprise-wide cooperation. One approach for this is to care for establishing network contracts that shall

define the governance, goals and liabilities of an enterprise network in order to reduce the possible risks of involvement for enterprises and increase business cooperation in general. However, there is a risk here for creating unnecessary bureaucratic hurdles and overheads without affecting positively at all the quality of collaborations.

Ukraine

Collaboration, both within Ukraine and on an international scale, should be embraced to leverage shared knowledge and best practices. Ultimately, the success of this initiative hinges on the collective commitment and synergistic efforts of all stakeholders involved ⁴⁶.

- **Establishing Strategic Academic Partnerships** is vital for mutual academic enrichment and sharing of knowledge. This will enable the cultivation of ecosystem ambassadors who can effectively communicate the strengths and opportunities of the Ukrainian innovation ecosystem.
- **Incorporating R&D through Academic Cooperation** will ensure access to specialised resources and foster a collaborative environment among academic institutions, research centres, and industry, which is especially crucial for fields like deep tech.
- **Engaging more with digital startups** may help companies to become more digital and create demand for new products
- **Corporations could become a partner** in providing distribution and marketing support, buying from and investing into startups, sharing information and data, mentoring and coaching startups.
- A higher level of **global connectedness to top ecosystems** helps startups generate higher sales and interact with consumers on global markets

⁴⁶ «Ukrainian Partnership. Kick-off workshop: Recap», Report by Expertise France and EU4Digital, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/13YCyDmyW9MxLMNUNnkiZF4OmTazukfHZ/view?usp=drivesdk>, (accessed September 25, 2023).

Challenges and Recommendations

- *Discuss challenges faced during the analysis process, such as data gaps or inhomogeneity of resources.*
- *Provide recommendations for addressing these challenges in future analyses.*

Challenges:

Some gaps or data resources that give challenges during the analysis process of the European entrepreneurial ecosystem were:

- **The lack of comparable and reliable data on the number, size, sector, stage, and performance of different categories of entrepreneurship** (start-ups, spin-off, self-entrepreneurs, women-led businesses) across the 6 countries, which makes it difficult to measure and benchmark the ecosystem's dynamism and impact .
- The lack of consistent and comprehensive data on the **funding sources, amounts, and terms of entrepreneurship** (start-ups, spin-off, self-entrepreneurs, women-led businesses) across the 6 assessed countries , which makes it hard to assess and compare the availability and accessibility of finance for the entrepreneurs.
- **The lack of qualitative and contextual data on the motivations, challenges, and opportunities of entrepreneurship** (start-ups, spin-off, self-entrepreneurs, women-led businesses) **as founders of different business entities and investors** across the 6 assessed countries, which makes it challenging to understand and address their needs and expectations
- **The lack of systematic and longitudinal data on the outcomes and impacts of the entrepreneurship** (start-ups, spin-off, self-entrepreneurs, women-led businesses) across the 6 assessed countries , such as **their survival rates, growth rates, job creation, innovation outputs, social and environmental contributions**, etc., which makes it problematic to evaluate and improve the ecosystem's effectiveness and efficiency.

Recommendations

One possible way to collect reliable data for future analysis of the European entrepreneurial ecosystem is to follow a common framework and methodology that can **capture the different dimensions and actors of the ecosystem**, as well as the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for each region. Another possible way is to learn from the experiences of existing projects that have mapped and analysed the entrepreneurial ecosystems of various European regions, such as the **Fostering collaboration across entrepreneurial ecosystems project**. This project developed a common framework and methodology to map the entrepreneurial ecosystems of 18 regions that were awarded the European Entrepreneurial Region label.

The project used regional indicators for ecosystem dynamism, interviews with ecosystem players, and SWOT analysis to produce in-depth mapping reports. The project also facilitated peer learning and action planning among the regions to foster interregional collaboration. A third possible way is to focus on specific aspects or domains of the entrepreneurial ecosystem that are relevant for the future analysis, such as financial, social, or environmental dimensions.⁴⁷

It can be studied on how to collect reliable data for future analysis of the European entrepreneurial ecosystem during the project lifecycle.

⁴⁷ https://cor.europa.eu/en/events/Documents/ECON/EER/EER_guidebook_final_draft_edited.pdf

Conclusion

- Key findings of the SWOT analysis for each entrepreneurial ecosystem.
- Recap the importance of working with local ecosystems and the potential impact of the matchmaking suggestions.

Greece

Greece's entrepreneurial ecosystem is an evolving landscape with a unique blend of traditional sectors and technological innovation. The ecosystem's strengths, such as sectoral expertise in maritime and energy, rich cultural heritage, and strong communal ties, position Greece as a promising hub for startups. However, challenges like bureaucratic complexities and limited early-stage funding need to be urgently addressed to realize this potential fully.

Key recommendations include simplifying business processes, fostering both local and international collaborations, and establishing dedicated funding mechanisms for early-stage startups. These strategies, led by various stakeholders like the government, industry leaders, and educational institutions, can serve as critical steps in enhancing Greece's entrepreneurial environment.

The sustainability and long-term vision of this ecosystem are promising. As traditional sectors increasingly intersect with technological advancements, there is a significant opportunity for innovative, sustainable growth. Programs that focus on social entrepreneurship also align well with global sustainability goals, opening doors for international funding and partnerships.

In conclusion, nurturing the entrepreneurial ecosystem is not just a pathway to economic prosperity but also a cornerstone for social development. A robust startup ecosystem can lead to job creation, social innovation, and the fortification of a community-centric ethos that is inherently Greek. Thus, a coordinated, focused approach to bolstering Greece's entrepreneurial ecosystem is not just desirable—it is imperative for the country's long-term economic and social well-being.

Bulgaria

Bulgaria's entrepreneurial ecosystem stands as a testament to the nation's resilience, adaptability, and potential for growth. With strengths such as a skilled talent pool, especially in the tech sector, supportive governmental policies, and a growing reputation as a tech and innovation hub in Southeast Europe, the country is poised for significant advancements. However, it also faces challenges, including negative demographic trends, a potential brain drain, and a regulatory environment that sometimes proves cumbersome for startups.

To harness the full potential of this ecosystem, several strategic initiatives are paramount. The government should prioritize investments in underrepresented sectors, foster international collaborations, and expand digital infrastructure. Additionally, promoting a culture of innovation through nationwide campaigns, workshops, and R&D incentives, coupled with institutionalizing mentorship programs, can provide startups with the necessary tools and guidance to thrive. Facilitating easier cross-border investment mechanisms and establishing twinning programs with other European entrepreneurial hubs can further enhance Bulgaria's global competitiveness.

In the broader context, Bulgaria's ambition to transition from an "emerging innovator" to a "moderate innovator" [39] is both commendable and achievable. The country has been making concerted efforts to boost its innovation performance, as evidenced by its strategic investments in the ICT sector and the establishment of tech clusters and research centres. The presence of multinational companies and their research hubs further amplifies Bulgaria's innovation potential. By aiming to elevate its status to a "moderate innovator", Bulgaria is not only setting a benchmark for its own progress but is also sending a clear message to the international community about its commitment to becoming a leading tech and innovation hub in Southeast Europe.

Turkiye

The entrepreneurial spirit in Turkiye is notably buoyed by its robust industries, burgeoning support infrastructure, and a somewhat conducive regulatory environment. However, it is imperative to underscore the necessity of fortifying the existing support structures and mitigating the challenges that could potentially stymie the growth trajectory of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Our analysis unveils a spectrum of critical elements pivotal to the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Turkiye. The strengths and opportunities identified within the ecosystem, such as the geographical location, skilled labour, and accumulated know-how, are juxtaposed with the inherent weaknesses and threats that permeate through aspects like the regulatory environment and collaboration

networks. The analysis further underscores the significance of technological innovations and market trends, particularly in technology and knowledge-intensive sectors like gaming, e-commerce, and various technological domains.

The recommendations and strategic insights proffered in this report underscore the pivotal role of fostering a collaborative ethos among stakeholders, enhancing the regulatory framework, and strategically leveraging the available opportunities to bolster the entrepreneurial ecosystem. It is paramount that concerted efforts be directed towards harnessing the identified opportunities, such as fostering B2B collaborations and leveraging digital transformation and AI automation, to propel the ecosystem to new heights.

In essence, the future trajectory of the Turkish entrepreneurial ecosystem is not merely a function of individual entities operating in isolation but is a collective tapestry woven through the deliberate and coordinated efforts of all stakeholders. It is through such a unified and strategic approach that the ecosystem will not merely navigate through its current challenges but will robustly thrive, enhancing its global positioning and contributing to the broader global entrepreneurial narrative.

France

From the beginning of the 2010s, aware of its lag in innovation, France has implemented a proactive strategy to catch up, with increasingly visible results. The creation of Bpifrance has made it possible to set up a one-stop shop for financing and supporting start-ups, thus compensating for the initial relative weakness of private funding. Launching the French Tech initiative in 2013 allowed France to structure its start-up ecosystem through a labeling system. France has been able to build up real momentum in venture capital financing, creating both institutional and private investing space. Still, France needs to channel savings towards investment in innovation, so that start-ups benefit from it. Tackling the talent shortage is a challenge for French Tech Ecosystem as France attracts international talent on one side, and loses its own on the other side.

The proposed actions therefore covers all the components that would improve the overall landscape of the French entrepreneurial ecosystem:

1. Continue the effort to entrepreneurship awareness. The study confirms the idea that France is becoming an entrepreneurial country. However, the entrepreneurial culture does not seem to permeate all of society. Actions are still necessary to remove certain obstacles. A very early work must be carried out to disseminate entrepreneurial standards and values. As the informants pointed out, France lags behind others richest countries on the issue of entrepreneurial education at the

primary and of secondary school. The policies carried out at the level of higher education carried their fruits including the creation of PEPITE and the implementation of national and regional policy and coordination. Seats on entrepreneurial education at the level of primary and secondary education would allow on the one hand to better understand good practices in France and abroad, and on the other hand to design a strategy adapted to diversity contexts.

2 Facilitate access to the market for new businesses

Starting a business often faces the difficulty of convincing customers who know neither the business nor sometimes even the product or service, in a context of innovation. Researchers in the field of entrepreneurship qualify this difficulty as a handicap or liability of newness which is added to the weight of smallness. To remedy this, new companies must succeed in building a certain legitimacy. This quest for legitimacy can be facilitated by obtaining contracts with large companies or administrations. The challenge is to encourage and facilitate access to markets for new businesses, but also to protect young businesses in these asymmetrical relationships. Significant efforts have been made by public authorities to facilitate access to public markets, such as LAW no. 2020-1525 of December 7, 2020 on the acceleration and simplification of public action, and the measures taken in the context the health crisis to facilitate public procurement. These actions aimed at VSEs/SMEs essentially take into account the size of the companies, the issue of age should be better taken into consideration.

3 Make female entrepreneurship a national policy

The share of women in business creation has progressed by 10 points in 20 years. According to INSEE, they represent 41% of creators (INSEE, 2022). However, for several years this share has stagnated around 40%. In 2021, the total entrepreneurial activity is 8.4% for men and 7.1% for women. Among the obstacles, the fear of failure is more marked among women than among men (53.1% vs 46.3%). The panel of experts points to a national culture that is not very conducive. The health crisis and teleworking have not improved the balance between private and professional life for women. Entrepreneurship is still stereotyped as “masculine”. The objective of achieving parity is realistic, but requires a collective commitment from society and entrepreneurial ecosystems. There is a wide diversity of actors who support female entrepreneurship on whom public authorities can rely if they wish to implement a national action plan in favor of female entrepreneurship. The world of education and the world of business have a decisive role to play in helping to change culture and encouraging forms of support such as mentoring or coaching.

4 Encourage consideration of sustainable development issues in the entrepreneurial projects

The health crisis has helped to relaunch the debate on the challenges of sustainable development. A slight majority of the entrepreneurs surveyed say they prioritize the social and/or environmental impact of their business, even before profitability or growth. A gap is emerging between supposed consideration and the implementation of actions. Around 69% of entrepreneurs say they take environmental implications into account. However, only 24% of emerging entrepreneurs and 49% of

established entrepreneurs implement actions to minimize the impact on the environment. 71.5% of emerging entrepreneurs and 58.6% of established entrepreneurs say they take social implications into account when making strategic decisions. But only 14.2% of emerging entrepreneurs and 26.1% of established entrepreneurs say they are implementing actions to maximize social impact. This places France in last position among the G7 countries. The challenge is not so much to raise awareness of sustainable development, but to support entrepreneurs in the implementation of concrete actions having a social and environmental impact. French policy makers therefore should sponsor and promote the creation of centers for entrepreneurship development and business incubators across the country by involving business schools. The need for custom-tailored entrepreneurial educational programs is necessary to solve the problem of the lack of entrepreneurial knowledge for founders when they need it. It is obvious that a new paradigm of French Tech is emerging, and every stakeholder in the ecosystem must quickly and vigorously adapt to this new reality. Once this is done, the French tech ecosystem can enter a new stage of its development. This will involve greater gender, ethnic, and social origin diversity, as well as greater uniqueness through a greater real risk-taking for entrepreneurs and funds.

In addition, the development of the ecosystem relies on a greater share of sustainable capital at the growth stage and resolving the lack of European growth capital. The development of the French Tech sector must also continue to “internationalize” both its mentality and language to attract experienced foreign operators.

Ireland

It was identified as **strengths** that Ireland possesses a unique position as a global hub, where top international companies locate their headquarters, but also in terms of attracting highly talented and young researchers and scientists who see the opportunity in having ease of access to global markets. Another strength is that researchers and scientists, especially those coming from other EU and non-EU countries, find it easier to build their own enterprise in Ireland than in other countries of the EU.

It was also identified as **weaknesses due to the** relatively high costs for running a company and acquiring services. What appears as attractive in terms of rather low social security costs as a percentage of personnel costs should be possibly reconsidered as a potential weakness. Last but not least the *need for strong networking and for entrepreneurs to build and operate their own business networks at national and regional level* may offer an advantage to people who have inhabited the Irish innovation ecosystem as e.g. the case of researchers and scientists who lived and worked in the Republic for several years but may still create difficulties when aiming access to funding, investors, opportunities, markets and customers.

It was identified as **opportunities**, amongst others, the superb access to funding instruments and support measures, especially and mainly if there are preexisting and / or longstanding links with the Irish higher education and research ecosystems. This opportunity pairs also with the opportunity of facing relatively reduced difficulties associated with accessing finance.

Finally, it was identified as **threats** the possible or potential *loss of the 'walk the extra mile' culture that distinguishes Ireland and the Irish ecosystem*; this might bring the mentality of finding solutions to problems and making things work to extinction. Such a development would result in a failure to support what we praised Ireland for deploying a 'business model of substance'. The development of prototypes of indicative or representative entrepreneurial instances is also an aspect that we consider as worth exploring. This might help overcome the current dominant logic of positive and negative frames which is, we have to admit, an inherent part of SWOT analysis in itself.

Weaknesses may never be overcome from within a single ecosystem if not successfully paired with or matched against opportunities appearing in some other 'competing' or 'competitive' ecosystem(s). In the knowledge economy especially the concept of zero sum game is not only obsolete but inherently wrong, providing a false base and ill-defined foundations for the edifice of entrepreneurship.

Ukraine

Ukraine is rebuilding Ukraine's ambitious National Recovery Plan was eagerly anticipated and favourably received by the international community. It makes little distinction between rebuilding the destruction caused by the war and accelerating Ukraine's sustainable economic growth. Ukraine, as a relatively young country, has adopted a consistent course of integration with the rest of Europe for the last several years. It is making constant efforts to modernize, implement reforms and successfully resist external military aggression. Being one of the largest countries in Europe, it also has a large and educated population. Still, Ukraine's potential as a high-tech development centre (incl. the space or military industry) and the country of scalable startups remains underrated. Today, the development of entrepreneurship is one of the most important factors in the socio-economic growth of Ukraine. The effective development of entrepreneurship creates a competitive environment for business entities of various types of economic activity for the development of which there are favorable conditions and a sufficient scale of resource potential, the interest of foreign and domestic investors. At the same time, the successful activity of entrepreneurship solves a number of important tasks, in particular, contributes to the replenishment of the budget,

saturation of the consumer market with goods and services, creates new jobs, increases the employment of the population, while reducing the unemployment rate.

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